

Gendering the Academy
and Research: combating
Career Instability and Asymmetries

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20

Reflexive working groups for selection committee members: 12 SSH and STEM test institutions

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GENERAL INTRODUCTION

This GARCIA Working Paper ‘Reflexive working groups for selection committee members: 12 SSH and STEM test institutions’ presents the collection of the reports on the reflexive working groups for selection committee members that were organized in the six GARCIA beneficiaries: Belgium, Iceland, Italy, the Netherlands, Slovenia, and Switzerland. The reflexive working groups were organized in two disciplines: Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).

The reflexive working groups for selection committee members are part of work package 7 of the GARCIA project. The GARCIA Project – Gendering the Academy and Research: combating Career Instability and Asymmetries – is concerned with the implementation of actions in European universities and research centres to promote gender equality and to prevent gender stereotypes and discriminations. Work package 7 focuses on the revealing of gender practices in the construction of scientific excellence in recruitment and selection procedures. The construction of scientific excellence is especially salient for the early stages of a scientific career, as the label of excellence can make the difference between the inclusion or exclusion of researchers in academia. Building on the D7.2 report on Gender practices in the construction of excellence (Herschberg, Benschop & Van den Brink, 2016), the reflexive working groups are developed for committee members and other key players involved in the recruitment and selection of early career researchers.

A reflexive working group is a type of interactive training that invites the participants to reflect on their own actions and behaviour in organization processes. It is a space to share and exchange experiences. The aims of reflexive working groups were threefold. First, to raise awareness among key players on how gender practices influence the selection process and the selection criteria, including conceptions of excellence. Second, to raise awareness that evaluation criteria are not objectified truths, and that evaluators’ conceptions of criteria differ in highly political selection processes. And third, to raise awareness of the gender practices in evaluation procedures that disadvantage women.

Reflexive working groups are thus designed to discuss the recruitment and selection procedures of early career researchers and how gender practices are key to the inclusion or exclusion of candidates. Each beneficiary reported on the organization, execution and evaluation of these reflexive working groups in their national and organizational context. They reported on the challenges and resistances that they encountered either during the organization of the working groups or during the execution of the working groups. Although the basis of the reflexive working groups was the same for every beneficiary, national and organizational context factors resulted in several differences between the beneficiaries. Yet, these differences resulted in a valuable overview of what the organization of a reflexive working group of this kind entails in different national and organizational contexts. This exemplifies that keeping in mind the context in which the reflexive working groups are to be organized is crucial for its effectiveness and success.

The collection of these reports will provide insight into the organization of reflexive working groups for selection committee members, the challenges and resistances that organizers came across in organizing and executing the reflexive working groups, learning points, and the main outcomes of these reflexive working groups at six European universities and research centres.

1. BELGIUM

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The objective of organizing reflexive working groups with recruitment committee members is twofold. We first wanted to promote, amongst committee members (most of them being full professor) a climate that decreases gender bias in evaluation moments. That was achieved by discussing, during the working groups, the main findings we made in previous working packages of the Garcia project regarding the question of gender bias in UCLouvain organisational culture. We secondly wanted to collect information about the selection criteria that are used in actual recruitment procedures. Discussing, in light of different findings of the Garcia project, evaluation criteria and the perception of what is “scientific excellence” with committee members permit us: 1/to collect information about how “scientific excellence” is conceived in recruitment procedures at UCLouvain and 2/ to raise awareness of gender practices and gender bias in recruitment among key players in recruitment procedures.

We performed two working groups with committee members. One in the IACCHOS Institute (SSH Institute of the UCLouvain) and one in the ELI Institute (Institute of earth and life sciences - STEM). As recruitment commissions are composed mainly of full professors, we invited to the working groups most of the full professors of the two institutes. We also particularly targeted professors who occupy or had occupied decisional functions within their institute or even within the central administration of the UCLouvain (among them: Dean, President of Institute, former Vice-rector, and former Rector).

UCL specific context of recruitment

Selection procedures at the postdoctoral level at UCLouvain can take different forms. Tenure-track recruitment procedures are particularly different from non-permanent postdoctoral research or teaching staff member recruitments. Tenure-track recruitments (at the level of “*chargé de cours*” (assistant or associate professor) or “*chercheur qualifié*” (research associate) are the most formal recruitment procedures. It is the only stage of the career for which an official recruitment committee is constituted to assess the scientific quality of the candidates. Non-permanent post-doctoral position generally does not imply the constitution of a selection commission and are often directly conducted by the primary investigator of a research project himself.

Tenure-track recruitment procedures also depend on the scientific career paths that exist. Two career paths exist in Belgian universities: appointment as permanent professor at a university and appointment as permanent research associate at the FNRS (Belgian Funds for Scientific Research). Selection procedures as university professor or as permanent researcher at the FNRS are different.

Working in the UCLouvain context we focused solely on selection procedures as permanent associate professor. This recruitment procedure is very formalised and similar in every institute of the UCLouvain. When a position opens, a job advertisement constituted of a precise profile description is widely distributed. In the same time, a local (i.e. within the Faculty where the position is located regarding teaching duties) recruitment committee is constituted. This committee typically gathers 3 or 4 full

professors from the Faculty and 2 external members generally coming from abroad. This tailor-made committee examines all the applications received and draws up a short-list with candidates that will be invited to a hearing. After the hearing, the committee produce a ranking of the candidates. This ranking (identifying generally one preferred candidate, in some cases two can be ranked as first) is transmitted to the central authority of the UCLouvain (the rectoral board, composed of the rector and vice-rectors). The rectoral board then invite the first-ranked candidate(s) for a hearing and make the final decision to appoint the candidate selected by the local recruitment committee. Generally the candidate selected by the local commission is appointed, but, in some uncommon cases, the rectoral board can decide that the first-ranked candidate does not demonstrate sufficient scientific achievement and decide to close up the procedure and postpone the appointment to the next year.

1.2 SET UP OF THE TASK

Two different workshops were organised with committee members. The first one with committee members from the STEM department (ELI) took place on March the 25th 2016 (11AM to 1PM), the second with committee members from the SSH department (IACCHOS) also on the 25th of March (2PM to 4PM).

1.2.1 STEM Department

Organization of the workshop

The first task to perform was to identify professors in the ELI that have taken part on a regular basis to recruitment committees. As it is very difficult to obtain the information about past recruitment procedures, we decided to invite to the workshop all the professors having the rank of “full professor”, namely 22 full professors. We send them an e-mail to invite them to what we called a “Workshop on the Garcia Project”. In this invitation we presented the Garcia project and explained that the aim of the workshop was to identified: 1/ the criteria of “academic success” and the evolution of “academic career” and 2/ to think about the impact of these two elements on gender inequality in academic career. 11 out of 22 responded to our call to participation, 11 didn’t give us an answer (despite the different reminders we sent them).

Among the 11 respondents, 6 were not available in the two weeks we intended to plan the meeting. 5 accepted to come on the 25th of March for a 2 hours meeting (11AM to 1PM). Finally one of them cancelled and 4 full professors took part to the meeting.

All of them had participated to recruitment procedures. One was a former member of the rectoral board of the university and took part to several recruitment procedures not only in the ELI, but in all institutes of the university during several years. A second one took part to several recruitment commissions within the ELI and recruits on a regular basis postdoctoral researchers for his own research unit. The third one is a senior professor who took part to two recruitment procedures in the last five years, he also was a member of an evaluation commission at the FWO (the Flemish Funds for Scientific Research) in charged of the recruitment of postdocs and permanent research associates of the FWO. The last one was a younger full professor who had not yet been involved in a recruitment

committee (to appoint an associate professor), but had several experiences with the recruitment of postdoc researchers for his research team.

Among the 22 full professors of the ELI, only two are women. None of them took part to the meeting, one didn't answer to the invitation, and the second one was interested in the project but was on sabbatical leave and could not participate.

Content of the discussions

We divided the meeting in three parts. In a first part, we presented the aim of the working group and some actual facts about the "leaky pipeline" phenomenon and the progressive disappearance of women in academic career in Belgium coming from the Garcia working paper 5. We then asked the participants to react and comment these statements.

In a second part, we presented the results of a first research about the conception of "academic excellence" realised at UCLouvain. Based on interviews made previously with recruitment committee members, we distinguished two different conceptions of what is scientific excellence at UCL. A first one we called the "nomination set of criteria" and a second that we called the "competition set of criteria". We then asked the participants to comment and discuss this distinction. We asked them if they agreed with this analytical distinction between these two sets of criteria that are used to evaluate the scientific quality of a candidate during recruitment procedures. We also asked them if these sets of criteria could, to a certain extent, serve as an impediment for women to access permanent research positions.

In a last round of discussion we asked the participants if they have any recommendations to make regarding gender inequalities in recruitment procedures at UCLouvain.

In the first round of discussion (discussing the leaky pipeline phenomenon). A first intervention was made saying that:

"I have been in two recruitment commissions recently. In both we recruited women, thus in our institute, gender inequalities, if we make the math, I don't believe that exist" (Prof. ELI 1)

This first statement was quickly dismissed by other participants. The second participant stated that gender inequalities in recruitment is not a novelty. That 20 years ago the same observation was already done and that the situation has not evolved much ever since. For this professor the explication of that phenomenon is that:

"Private life concerns are more important to women candidates than to men".
(Prof. ELI 2).

After this observation the discussion went mostly around the difficulty for women to articulate their "working life" with their "family life". One interesting observation in this regard was that:

"As well as it is the case for men, women have all to gain from a career management policy that takes into account the family life" (Prof. ELI 3)

Three out of the four participants totally agreed with this statement and also agreed that expectations put on men and women regarding investment in work and family had known an "extraordinary evolution" and that the "pressure [on both men and women] is now

bigger than before”. Only one participant disagreed with this statement and found that work pressure is now lower than 30 years ago and that gender inequalities in this regard does not exist (Prof. Eli. 1).

It is also worth noting that during this round of discussion about the leaky pipeline phenomenon, men and women were regularly presented as, “biologically” or even “naturally” different and that those natural differences play a role in how research is done. Men were described as “dominant male”, more prone to adopt “blunt” or “animal” comportments, and that the presence of more women in the work environment make it more difficult to behave in this masculine manner. Women doctoral student were described as “more cautious”: - “they take 18 months to go to the lab for the first time” - than male PhD student that “when they have an idea, they have an idea, they fail and then they start again”. “They get the same result in the same time, but this is a reality” (Prof. Eli 2).

The second round of discussion was devoted to the discussion of how to assess academic excellence in recruitment procedures. We presented our analytical distinction (nomination criteria vs. competition criteria) and asked the participants if this distinction made sense regarding their experience.

The four participants agreed with our distinction. Competition criteria (impact factor, number of publications, postdoctoral abroad research stays...) were seen as more useful to write a first short-list of candidates, and “nomination criteria (the ability to fit in the department, human and social competencies, capacity to be autonomous) were seen as more important for the last round of audition. Our formulation of the distinction between these two set of criteria was judged quite robust and applicable to their experiences.

In the last round of discussion we asked the participation which recommendations they would set regarding fight against gender inequalities. A first set of recommendations are about the enhancement of the work environment. Diminution of the work pressure with measures like the diminution of meetings, the organisation of meetings during strict business hours (before 5PM), the diminution of administrative tasks. This diminution of work pressure would allow men and women to achieve a better work/life balance.

The second set of recommendation is about the setting up of an institutional gender policy. One of the professor thinks that the university should be more proactive in that matter and have an official gender policy. Another professor think that this gender policy should be linked to the formulation of a “family policy”. The university should communicate more about work/life balance.

1.2.2 SSH Department

Organization of the workshop

We launched a first round of invitations to professors that we know had taken part in recruitment committees in the last years. IACCHOS has 11 full professors (“*professeur ordinaire* ou “*professeur extra-ordinaire*”). We invited three of them but also different professors who have institutional responsibilities (directors of research units, members of the board of the institute), that we know have also been involved in recruitment procedures. We thus invited 11 people to the working group. We send them an e-mail to

invite them to what we called a “Workshop on the Garcia Project”. In this invitation we presented the Garcia project and explained that the aim of the workshop was to identify: 1/ the criteria of “academic success” and the evolution of “academic career” and 2/ to think about the impact of these two elements on gender inequalities in academic career. The 11 professors answered our e-mail and have shown some interest in the project. Among them, 5 were interested but were not available during the two weeks we intended to plan the meeting. Finally two professors cancelled in last minute (for medical reasons) and four professors took part in the meeting on March the 25th (2PM to 4PM).

All of them had participated to recruitment procedures in the past years. One (a full professor) was a former member of the rectoral board of the university and took part to several recruitment procedures, not only in the IACCHOS. A second one (full professor) was a former president of the IACCHOS institute and took part to several recruitment procedures in the Institute but also in other Institutes. Two (1 full professor and 1 professor, director of a research unit) took part to some recruitments procedures in the IACCHOS only.

We contacted three women and eight men. Three men took part to the meeting and one woman. (Among the 11 full professors of IACCHOS, 2 are women).

Content of the discussions

As it was the case for the ELI working group, we divided the meeting in three parts. In a first part, we presented the aim of the working group and some actual facts about the “leaky pipeline” phenomenon and the progressive disappearance of women in academic career in Belgium coming from the Garcia working paper 5. We then asked the participants to react and comment these statements.

In a second part, we presented the result of a first research about the conception of “academic excellence” realised at UCLouvain. Based on interviews made previously with recruitment committee members, we distinguished two different conceptions of what is scientific excellence at UCL. A first one we called the “nomination set of criteria” and a second that we called the “competition set of criteria”. We then asked the participants to reflect on this distinction. We asked them if they agreed with this analytical distinction between these two sets of criteria that are used to evaluate the scientific quality of a candidate during recruitment procedures. We also asked them if these sets of criteria could, to a certain extent, served as an impediment for women to access permanent research positions.

In a last round of discussion we asked the participants if they have any recommendations to make regarding gender inequalities in recruitment procedures at UCLouvain.

In the first round of discussion, the four participants agreed to the fact that the leaky pipeline phenomenon (the disappearance of women in academic career) is a reality, but that the situation could vary across the different institutes of the university. One of the participant who is also affiliated to the Institute of economy pointed out that in this institute, there is only two female professors and that in the last 6 recruitments, all the selected candidates were males. They all agreed that the situation was better in the social science institute (at some point, one of the participant even expressed concern about the possible “lack of men, which could be worrying [referring to the student population in some disciplines]” (Prof. IACS, 4).

In this regard, one participant expressed that:

“If I speak for myself, it’s a criteria [the sex] that I never have seen as important. Woman or man, I have always felt like I hired the most competent person for the job” (Prof. IACS, 3).

The four candidate agreed however that it was uncommon to find women at institutional important positions. One noted that the UCLouvain has never had a woman as rector and that in fact in Belgian French-speaking universities, only one of the universities had once a female rector for a few years.

The first speaker in the roundtable stated that the fact that women were underrepresented in universities and were given less responsibilities was “highly regrettable” (Prof. IACS 3). He noted that in the last recruitment procedures he/she attended, they decided that, if two candidates were ranked first regarding their competencies, and if one candidate is a women and the other a men, they would chose the women for this reason.

The four participant highlighted the fact that is was highly difficult for women to work in universities and to have a harmonious family life. One of the participant stated for example that:

“in the institute of economics, it is impossible to be a women and to have children”. (Prof. IACS 1, also affiliated to the institute of economics).

Another professor (Prof. IACS 2) noted that in its research unit, there is three female professors and that none of them have children. He also noted that all the postdoctoral temporary researchers were women that:

“Were looking for a permanent academic job, but were also looking to equilibrate their family life. Regarding their level of mobility, one comes from France, one from Sweden, one from Poland, one from China and one from Belgium. The Swedish has a husband and kids in Sweden. The others, they have a boyfriend in Paris or in Luxembourg and they move between the two places, they are really in an uncomfortable situation.”

At the end of the round of discussion one of the participant summarized the exchange in this way:

“ – (Prof. IACS 4) I’m tempted to say that the main entry to the question is the question of gender and not the question of sex, because, finally, the women who achieve to get a career are those who *ape* (imitate) the men, those who do not have children etc. And the men who are today in difficulties are those who *ape* the women by taking care of their kids...

– (Prof. IACS 1) Yes, there is no discrimination on basis of sex.

– (Prof. IACS 3) Yes, we agree”

To sum up they agreed that the leaky pipeline phenomenon was linked to the difficulty to articulate a family life with the criteria of academic productivity and that this problem was mainly encountered by women. They noted however that this difficulty can also be a source of difficulties for men.

The second round of discussion was devoted to the discussion of how to assess academic excellence in recruitment procedures. We presented our analytical distinction (nomination criteria vs. competition criteria) and asked the participants if this distinction made sense regarding their experiences.

The first reaction was to discuss the distinction between “competition” criteria and “nomination” criteria. The first participant pointed out that when he read this distinction that he first thought that “competition criteria” were mainly about research and “nomination criteria” were mainly about the other missions of universities (teaching and community services). He also disagreed with the term “nomination”. According to him a better label for this set of criteria would be “integration”. He noted that:

“The way you separated these two set of criteria shows the hierarchy of activities in universities. (...) With this distinction teaching seems unimportant, except, maybe, at the time in the selection processes where you assess the “nomination” [the capacity of integration]” (Prof. IACS 3)

A second participant linked the criteria of competition to the growing importance of international ranking initiatives of universities. He stated that:

“The competition comes in the system because we adopted the ranking system. The UCLouvain authorities went in that system and say that they want to play with the best. It’s the reason why the criteria of competition are put forward today. You need publications, you need international mobility.” (Prof. IACS 4)

He interestingly linked this observation with a recommendation regarding the work/family balance:

“I think that it is one of the criteria [mobility] on which we can leverage. One can be involved in international network without leaving our offices. I think that we really can be ‘international’ without moving a lot. It is interesting for those who want to invest in family.” (Prof. IACS 4)

A last professor pointed that when recruiting an assistant professor:

“We want everything. (...) The first criteria are research focused. Universities are the only places where we do research so it does not surprise me that research is important in recruitment commissions. (...) But I’m struck by the quality of discussion in recruitment commissions. A lot of criteria are used. The question of integration is also very important.” (Prof. IACS 1).

In the last round of discussion we asked the participants which recommendations they would set regarding fight against gender discrimination. A first set of recommendation is linked to the indicators used to assess the “competition” or the “productivity” of a researcher.

It was suggested that the “CV bodybuilding” techniques was not the best practice to follow. Rather than listing all his/her publication, a candidate could for example only send his two best articles that would be read by the committee. Rather than listing the amount of months he/she stays abroad, the candidate could, in his/her CV demonstrate his/her

embeddedness in international networks by the connexion he/she has or the achievement he made through international collaboration.

A second type of recommendation was related to the composition and the functioning of the recruitment commissions. It was suggested that plurality (regarding sex) should be a priority when constituting a commission. On participant stated that:

“It is important to achieve a plurality of points of view in the commission. Include women in commission is important, not for quota reason, but to have the point of view of women that would maybe be more prone to understand the personal difficulties of candidate”.

It was also suggested that it would be a better solution to proceed to the hiring of most that one professor in one session of recruitment as a way to have the possibility to choose different candidates judged excellent according to different set of criteria.

A last set of recommendations is linked to the articulation of private and professional time. To this regard, one professor noted that the growing flexibility between working time and family time was highly difficult for young researcher:

“I think that a new difficulties today is the porosity between professional life and personal life. I bless the lord that I began to work 10 year before my young colleagues. For young researcher, now, flexibility and porosity between work time and family time is an impediment as much for family that it is for work. » (Prof. IACS 1)

A second recommendation in this regard was the idea that post-doctoral grant systems should be more aware of the family situation of the researcher. It is still difficult for some excellent researchers to go abroad. Post-doctoral grants should help in this regard.

1.3 EVALUATION OF THE TASK

When performing the two workshops, our main objective was to create a learning environment by raising the awareness that evaluation criteria are not objectified truths and that evaluators' conceptions of criteria differ. The creation of this learning environment would promote a climate that decreases gender bias in evaluation moments.

We will now evaluate the two workshops with this objective in mind. We will identify 1/ what have worked when performing the working groups, 2/ what challenges and resistances we encountered, 3/ what learning points we gain from planning the working groups and 4/ The specificity of the UCLouvain context and what future action could be undertaken.

What worked when performing the working groups?

The way we structured the discussions, with three rounds of discussion around the presentation of previous research results of the Garcia project was very effective. It sparked fruitful discussions in both working groups (ELI and IACCHOS), and permitted to clearly address the question of gender inequality in academic career with full professors

who are generally male in their fifties and could maybe not be often sensitized to the question of gender inequality at the universities.

The format of the working groups: 4 participants, 2 hours, 3 members of the Garcia project to lead the discussions was plainly effective. The experiences conducted show that, even if our first goal was to gather 6 or 7 participants in every working groups, 4 participants could be an efficient amount of participants for a two hours working groups. Every participant could talk approximatively 20 minutes and a sufficient amount of time was still available for debates among participants. The possibility to create debate among participant permit to build some consensuses among gender inequalities and how to prevent them in recruitment procedures. More crowded working groups would certainly have given less time for collective discussion (has we organised our rounds of discussion with a first individual roundtable before launching the debate) and hence for building consensuses.

We decided to contact potential participants by sending a personal invitation by e-mail. This medium was quite effective. We actually were surprised by the actual response rate to the first wave of invitations. In our protocol we had seen e-mail invitation as a first contact that should certainly be completed with direct contacts (through phone) to convinced full professors and research unite directors (that generally have a very busy schedule) to take part to our working groups. E-mail were sufficient and permit us to gather professors who had occupied very high responsibility in the university (e.g. two former member of a rectoral team, and a former president of Institute).

What challenges and resistances we encountered?

We did not encounter much organisational difficulty to organise the two working groups. The bigger difficulty was located in the sensitive content of the discussions and linked to the fact that it was apparently difficult for the participants to recognise that actual gender inequalities or sexual discrimination could exist in their institute.

In both cases, the participants were keen to recognise that gender inequalities or sexual discriminations is a problem in universities. They also agreed with the analysis in term of leaky pipeline. But in the two working groups, they generally presented their institute as a place where these inequalities or discriminations were either non-existent (“I have been in two recruitment commissions recently. In both we recruited women, thus in our institute, gender inequality, if we make the math, I don’t believe that exists” (Prof. ELI 1)) or if not non-existent, smaller than in other institutes (with the institute of economy designated as the worst case scenario in the two working groups, where: “it is impossible to be a women and to have children”).

The fact that gender discrimination was generally recognised as a general problem in universities is a starting point permitting to raise the question of how to fight these inequalities but the fact that the different professors involved in our workshops had difficulties to see their work environment as problematic to this regard is in itself problematic. This characteristic made difficult the evolution of the debate around how to actually produce changes in ELI or IACCHOS.

What learning points we gain from performing the working groups

We presented during the two workshops the analytical distinction we forged in a previous phases of the Garcia project opposing the criteria of “competition” to the criteria of “nomination” used in academic recruitment at UCLouvain. The validity of that distinction was disused heavily in both working groups.

Even if the main rationales behind this analytical distinction was validated, alternative labels were proposed and the place of these criteria in actual recruitment processes was heavily discussed.

At the end of the workshop, we think that this distinction can be used to give a better understanding of the causes of the leaky pipeline phenomenon. The input we gain during the workshops will enable us to elaborate this distinction further.

What was specific for our context, which future working group leaders need to take into account?

One of the difficulties in the UCLouvain context is that it is often difficult to know how recruitment commissions are composed. We overcame this difficulty by targeting directly all the full professors of the ELI and some of the full professor and the research unit directors of the IACCHOS. This strategy could maybe not be the best strategy in every universities where rules for constituting recruitment committees could be different.

Another specificity of the UCLouvain context is that in every Institute, most of the professor already knows each other's. We didn't had to plan a moment during the working groups for presentation and breaking glass activities. Discussions could begin immediately. Two hours were thus sufficient for our working groups. Working with people that did not have this previous knowledge could need to extend the two hours duration of the working group.

If we had to plan other working groups in UCLouvain for full professors, we would proceed in the same way. Discussion in small groups seems to be a good way to raise awareness about gender inequalities.

1.4 CONCLUSION

We can conclude that the working groups we organised were an efficient first attempt to raise awareness about gender practices in recruitment procedures. In both cases, we achieved to produce fruitful discussions about gender inequalities and to transmit valuable insights from the Garcia project that were accepted by the participants.

The main difficulty was to overcome the fact that in both workshops, if participant were keen to recognise gender inequalities as a general problem for universities, they tend to minimise the prevalence of this problem in their institute. This phenomenon was similar in the STEM and the SHS Institute.

We can however observe differences between the responses to the results of previous Gracia work that we presented in the two institutes. Professors of the SHS Institute were more familiar with the question of gender and tended to distinguish clearly the question of gender inequalities from the question of sexual discriminations. This distinction was less clear for the professors of the STEM institute.

In both institute the discussion of the leaky pipeline phenomenon led to the question of the possibility, for young researcher (and certainly for women), to achieve a good personal/working life balance. The question of having children or to have the willingness to “invest in family” was clearly connected to the question of the indicators of academic excellence (number of publications, abroad experiences...). In both workshops, it was recognised that it was important for any individual to achieve a good family/work balance. Both working groups made the recommendation that personal situations (e.g. having children during the realisation of the PhD, etc.) should be part of evaluation, and that potential excellent candidates (men or women) could “disappear” from university for this reason.

As actual inequality in the institute were not merely recognised it was difficult to engage the discussion about the setting up of actual action plans to reduce gender inequality. Some general recommendations have been made (see 2.1. and 2.2.). But no formal engagement have been made.

A first step for future actions should thus to promote the idea that, if gender inequalities is recognised as an actual and documented problem in universities, it is a problem everywhere, in every Institute.

2. ICELAND

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The main objective of the reflexive working group was to raise awareness among evaluation and selection committee members, the specialists that work with the committees in the process and the key Equal Rights body at University of Iceland about the construction of excellence and gender practices in the evaluation and selection processes and practices and to promote a climate that decreases the likelihood of gender bias in the selection of candidates.

The University of Iceland is organised into five academic schools with 25 faculties and four interdisciplinary study lines. The selection process takes place in two stages as determined by the Rules for the University of Iceland No. 569/2009. First an evaluation committee evaluates if candidates fulfil the minimum requirements for the position. The evaluation committee consists of three members, two members appointed by the University council and one specialist appointed by the faculty (department). The applications of qualified candidates are sent to the selection committee. After the evaluation committee has evaluated candidates, the selection committee takes over in order to make the final decision on who is going to be hired for the position. The evaluation committee consists of five members, the head of the faculty that is also the chair of the committee. One standing member appointed by the faculty. Two specialists appointed by the faculty and one member appointed by the University's rector. When it comes to participation in the evaluation and selection committees it is stated in the Act on Equal Status and Equal Rights of Women and Men no. 10/2008 that participation of women and men in public committees and boards has to be approximately equal (minimum 40%), this also applies to these committees. The Division of Human Resources and the Division of Science and Innovation at the University of Iceland work with the committees during the evaluation and selection process.

In order to make gender equality procedures in the evaluation and selection process sustainable at University of Iceland it is important that this is a top down process and applicable to all the five academic schools. The Icelandic GARCIA team saw an opportunity to collaborate with the University of Iceland's Equal Rights Committee in organizing the reflexive working group. The Equal Rights Committee is expected, according to the University of Iceland's Equal Rights Policy 2013-2017, to put together guidelines for the integration of equality dimensions in hiring and promotion. Therefore one working group was organised with all the standing members of the evaluation and selection committees in the School of Engineering and Natural Sciences (STEM) and the School of Social Sciences (SSH) and the staff at the Division of Human Resources and the Division of Science. The Equal Rights committee will use the outcomes of Task 7.1 and 7.2 and the outcomes of the working group to build their guidelines. The GARCIA team members see this collaboration as an opportunity to make sure that the outcomes of the project will be used as a tool to bring awareness to evaluation and selection committee members on the gender practices and the construction of excellence in the appointment processes, that will be applicable to all the academic schools and potential step towards transforming the evaluation and selection practices within the University of Iceland towards a more gender equal processes.

Invitations to participate in the reflexive working groups were sent to all the standing members of the evaluation and selection committees in STEM and SSH, the specialists at the Division of Human Resources and the Division of Science that work with the committees, the University of Iceland's Equal Rights committee members and the University of Iceland's Equal Opportunities Officer. The reflexive working group took place on Thursday April 28th 2016 at 12:00 - 14:00 at the National and University Library of Iceland. In attempt to attract participants the meeting was arranged around noon and a light lunch was offered in the beginning of the meeting. An invitation to participate in the reflexive working groups was sent out on April 11th 2016 and a reminder sent out on April 22nd 2016.

2.2 SET UP OF THE TASK

2.2.1 STEM and SSH department: The School of Engineering and Natural Sciences and the School of Social Sciences

All standing committee members, that take part in the evaluation and selection process in STEM and SSH, were invited to participate in the reflexive working group. This includes the evaluation committee members appointed by the University council, the heads of faculties (that are the chairs of the selection committees), the standing members appointed by the faculty and the standing members appointed by the University's rector. In total 22 committee members in SSH and 23 committee members in STEM. Two specialists, one from the Division of Human Resources and one from the Division of Science and Innovation that work with the committees were invited. Furthermore, the Equal Rights Committee and the Equal opportunities officer were invited, in total nine people. Out of the 59 participants invited ten participants attended, four committee members, the two specialists from the Division of Human Resources and from the Division of Science and Innovation, and four people that work with equality issues within the University. What was notable was that none of the SSH committee members attended the reflexive working group.

The working group took place in a conference room at the National and University Library of Iceland. Tables were round up in an U-shape to facilitate discussion. Professor Þorgerður Einarsdóttir and Assistant professor Gyða Margrét Pétursdóttir, members of the Icelandic GARCIA team, led the working groups and presented the findings of Task 7.1. and 7.2. via a projector. The working group was divided into five sessions. The first session was an introduction of the GARCIA group and project, the collaboration with the University Councils Equal Rights Committee on making guidelines of integration of equality dimension in hiring and promotion and the goals of the working groups were explained.

In the second session the working group facilitators presented the methodology of task 7.1 and 7.2, the gender representation of academic staff in STEM and SSH in 2013, the criteria put forward in the job description of the advertised positions of assistant professors, the differences in the job descriptions of STEM and SSH, the positions advertised in STEM and SSH in 2013, information on the candidates that applied by gender and the candidates that were selected by gender. Following that session, participants in the working groups were asked to pair up and discuss this information for five minutes.

Following that the working group facilitators opened up the discussion on the topic and asked: What angle can we take on this information? How can we interpret this information? What is the first thing that comes to mind? The participants shared their surprise on the prevalent gender segregation in STEM and SSH. The most discussed was the success rate of women and men and how that measurement can be misleading. The specialist from the Division of Science and Innovation revealed that even though the overall success rate is more positive for women it still doesn't expose the full story, he mentions that it is quite common that 75 men and 5 women apply for a position, and if a woman gets one position the success rate for women increases.

In the third session the working group facilitators presented the formal criteria put forward in the job description of the advertised positions, from what is most common to least common, and compared it to the criteria put forward in the University's regulation, that is: Research, teaching and administration. Following the session, participants in the working groups were asked to pair up and discuss this information for five minutes, then the working group facilitators opened up the discussions and asked: Why is the criteria put forward in this order? Is it based on importance? If equally important, why is it not put forward in an alphabetical order? Here the working group participants pointed out that this is based on the criteria put forward in the Evaluation System for Public Higher Education Institutions. Here it becomes apparent how the NPM funding incentives active at the University of Iceland, that are described in detail in the Icelandic report on gender budgeting (D5.1), impact other processes within the academic institution, such as the evaluation of candidates of job openings.

In the fourth session the working group facilitators presented the actual practices compared to the formal criteria and the differences between STEM and SSH. The result show that there is more emphasis on 'excellence' in STEM than in SSH, and that the criteria seems to be more flexible in SSH than in STEM. The outcomes reveal that salaries offered to selected candidates have different impact in STEM than in SSH, with it being common problem that selected candidates in STEM do not accept the position at University of Iceland due to low salaries in comparison to universities in other countries. This, however, is not the case in SSH. The group facilitators also presented how the objective criteria 'fitting into the team' plays a part in the selection process at both schools but differently. In STEM the candidate has to be able to work with the team on research and therefore it is important that the candidate fits into the team. In SSH the academics seem to work more alone and the candidate has to bring something new into the research field, therefore the emphasis is more that the candidate has to fit in the group socially because the academics won't be working together on research projects. Furthermore, the group facilitators presented how the formal criteria 'administration' is not considered to be important in the actual practice, how 'teaching' is considered more important in the formal practices than in the actual practices, and that 'teaching' is a criteria that is applied when in need. In addition, the outcomes reveal gender is not considered important in the selection process in STEM but in SSH, however, there is an aura of gender equality reigning in the selection process. With the general view being that gender equality has been reached at the School except in the female dominated fields, such as the Faculty of Social Work.

The fifth session was aimed on giving an input to the guidelines on integration of equality dimension in hiring and promotion. The working group facilitators presented what the

Equal Rights Committee has to keep in mind when making the guidelines, based on the GARCIA teams findings in task 7.1 and 7.2. Starting with the job description in the advertisement, it is necessary that the Equal Rights Committee keeps in mind the following questions: What is advertised? Who decides what is put forward in the job description? Who designs the job description? Is the job description 'gender blind'? Does a 'gender blind' job description eliminate gendered interpretation and practices? Is any criteria put forward in the job description subjective? Following that the focus was on the potential candidates, the following questions have to be kept in mind: What candidates are encouraged to apply for the positions? Are the academic staff using their networks? Are the academic staff asking their current and former students to apply? Are the sessional teachers and other staff holding a PhD within the University of Iceland being encouraged to apply? Can acquaintanceship have direct/indirect impact in the "encouragement" process? Is it possible to use that impact to make change in the gender composition instead of maintaining the status quo? Following that the focus was on the criteria required and the gendered practices, and the importance of looking at the following points: By requiring international experience are all the candidates receiving equal treatment? Family responsibilities, how should we and how can we approach that subject in the evaluation and selection process? How do we value "good foreign universities"? Since that is considered rather important criteria in the actual practices. What about the University of Iceland's responsibility when it comes their own PhD candidates, since the academic institution aims, according to its policy, to graduate 70 PhD candidates annually. Acquaintanceship/nepotism was most discussed in the fifth session, something that all participants saw as an important aspect in the selection process. However, the participants were sceptical on the idea that nepotism could be nourished within the University of Iceland because, they strongly believed, a candidate would always be selected because of merit. In discussion on how to diminish nepotism, the participants see opportunities in having foreign specialists participating as the external members of the selection committee. That however is however not that common in the selection committees.

Following the fifth session there was a short coffee break, where the participants were asked to pair up and discuss, based on the findings and their own experience, what else needs to be kept in mind when making the guidelines on integration of equality dimension in hiring and promotion. Following the coffee break the pairs presented their ideas to other members of the working group. The criterion a PhD from a "good foreign university" was a popular discussion, participant voiced their reservations towards selecting candidates from the University of Iceland because of the danger of 'academic inbreeding'. The workshop facilitators participated in that conversation by asking questions on mobility, such as: Do all candidates have the same opportunities to fulfil the criterion of attaining higher education in a foreign country? If 'academic inbreeding' is a weakness for the University of Iceland, then why is it put forward in the University's policy to graduate 70 PhD candidates every year? Is precariousness in academia a gendered reality? From that point of view, the discussion turned to other gendered aspects of the evaluation candidates in the selection process: Which candidates do have more family responsibilities? How does that impact their career? Can the committee members evaluate candidates with that perspective in mind? And if so, how can they do that?

The sixth session continued to aim at factors that are important to take into a consideration when putting together guidelines on integration of equality dimension in hiring and promotion. The working group facilitators further presented the outcomes of task 7.1 and 7.2, with the focus on what is most often considered the three most important formal criteria in the selection process: research, teaching and administration. In relation to the outcomes regarding the criterion 'research' the group facilitators asked the following questions: Is all research equally 'interesting theoretical input' for the faculty? Is the definition of 'interesting theoretical input' always the same or is there room for interpretation? What are the 'needs of the faculty'? Should the focus be on the existing fields within the University or is it important to develop new fields? Is 'age', 'production' and 'success' relative concepts? How do we define family responsibilities? Is that just the number of months of maternity/paternity leave or various responsibilities spanning the life cycle? How is it possible to value these aspects? Should there be a quantified measurement developed and applied to all selection cases? Is that possible? Or should it be evaluated by each individual case? How can the arbitrary decisions in the selection process be minimized? The participants made very interesting points regarding maternity/paternity leave and production of scientific output, and according to their feeling the leave does not impact the candidate until many years after the leave. This is because before taking a leave the candidates most often have been writing and submitting articles, the gap that the leave creates will not impact their production during or relatively close after the leave, but it is more likely to impact the candidates output five years after the leave. Regarding the formal criterion 'teaching', the group facilitators asked the following questions: Does quantity matter? How is that evaluated? In the years of experience or the number of courses taught? How are teaching evaluations utilized? Is it taken into consideration that teaching evaluations is a defective tool/measurement? Is it taken into consideration the size of the courses taught, in terms of ECTS credits and number of students? How about the different student/teacher ratio between faculties and fields? Is it taken into account that more workload in relation to teaching can impact success in research? Regarding the criterion 'administration', the group facilitators asked the following questions: When does administration matter? What administration is considered important? Is the criterion on 'communication skills' intertwined with the criterion of administration skills? Furthermore, the group facilitators asked: What are 'communication skills'? What has to be kept in mind when evaluating those 'skills'? How are personal traits treated in the selection process and does it impact women and men equally? All participants except one related to the discussion on personal traits being applied to women and men differently and it resulted in lively discussion on the matter. A female participant pointed out that a man is with certain personal traits can be considered a leader while a woman in the same position would be considered a pushy person or a "bitch". Another participant pointed out that the words used to describe a good leader are very similar to the words used to describe masculinity. The participant that did not relate to this was still not convinced after the discussion.

Following this session, the participants were asked to pair up again and discuss for five minutes, based on the findings presented in the working groups and their own experience, what else do they consider important to keep in mind when making a guidelines on integration of equality dimension in hiring and promotion. Participants were encouraged to write down cues during their conversation, and in the following discussions these action points and recommendations came forward:

- Participants voiced their opinion that the guidelines on the integration of equality dimensions in hiring and promotion needs to take into account the whole process, including the writing of the job description.
- Participants pointed out the importance of a gender equality specialists reading over the job description, in order to make sure that the job description is not 'gender blind' and this potentially gender biased.
- In the job description advertised candidates of the gender that is in minority within the faculty should be encouraged to apply for the position, in accordance to the Act on Equal Status and Equal Rights of Women and Men no. 10/2006. There were different opinions on the need for that recommendation; some candidates believe that 'affirmative action' like that is out-dated. Here it became apparent the resistance towards 'affirmative action' within the academic institution, even though this would be considered very moderate action. However, other participants see it as an important measure to challenge the systematic discrimination within the University of Iceland.
- Participants suggested that criteria is predefined and/or quantified in the evaluation and selection process with the purpose of minimizing arbitrary decision making processes. The following criteria and questions came up regarding this suggestion: How are 'communication skills' evaluated? How are personal traits treated in the selection process? How do those traits impact the evaluation of women and men? Would they result in different opinions of the candidates based on their gender?
- Regarding the selection of a candidate the participants often referred to the Act on Equal Status and Equal Rights of Women and Men no. 10/2006, especially article 26 where it is stated that if two or more applicants for a position are equally qualified, an applicant shall be chosen of the gender that is in minority of that area of work. However, the outcomes of task 7.1 and 7.2 show that there is little or no experience with applying this article in the selection process at University of Iceland. Participant in the working group pointed out that this law should be elevated in the selection process and should be a recommendation in the guidelines on the integration of equality dimensions in hiring and promotion.

The University of Iceland's Equality Committee is committed to make use of the outcomes of task 7.1 and 7.1 and the actions points that were the results of the working groups. According to the chair, the Equality Committee will build, on these outcomes and recommendations, the guidelines on the integration of equality dimensions in hiring and promotion, as required by the University of Iceland Equal Rights Policy 2013-2017. The matter will be discussed at the committee's meeting in the following weeks.

2.3 EVALUATION OF THE TASK

2.3.1 STEM and SSH department: The School of Engineering and Natural Sciences and the School of Social Sciences

When considering what worked when planning and performing the working groups there were two main elements that made the task successful. First, the collaboration with the University of Iceland Equal Rights Committee. In order to make the implementation successful it is important that it happens at the central university level, not the individual school level, and that the mandate comes from top administration and the formal equality bodies at the university. The Equal Rights Committee oversees matters of equality at the University of Iceland on behalf of the rector and the University Council. That, also, increases the likelihood that the task can be extended to all the academic schools. Second, connecting the task to the University of Iceland Equal Rights Policy and to the making of the guidelines on integration of equality dimension in hiring and promotion. The guidelines are one of the measure in the Equal Rights Policy to integrate equality dimensions into planning and decision making at the University of Iceland. Because of the collaboration with the Equal Rights Committee it was important that the outcome of the working group would be applicable to all the academic school within University of Iceland, therefore it was more suitable to have one working group with STEM and SSH committee members. By collaborating with the official equality body and building on active equality processes within the academic institution we believe that we are not only giving the implementation of the task, that is raising awareness on the construction of excellence and the gender practices in the selection process, credibility but also increasing the likelihood of the outcomes of the tasks 7.1 and 7.2 being implemented successfully, and hence sustainably.

Furthermore, it is very positive that all relevant parties, that is the members of the evaluation and selection committees, the staff from the Division of Human Resources and the Division of Science and Innovation work with the committees during the evaluation and selection process, the Equal Rights Committee and the GARCIA team were included in the making of the guidelines on integration of equality dimensions in hiring and promotion. The working group created an open space to reflect upon the processes and open up the possibility for all actors to give their input into the guidelines and reflect critically on the processes. Furthermore, by inviting the staff from the Division of Human Resources and the Division of Science and Innovation that work with the committees during the evaluation and selection process, we are securing that all participants in the selection process are aware of the construction of excellence and the gender practices in the selection of candidates.

The biggest challenge in planning and performing the working groups was to get the committee members to participate in the working group. In attempt to attract more participants, the working group was arranged to meet the needs of the academic staff, that is by arranging it after the spring teaching period, before the examination period, during normal working hours, around noon with a light lunch. This however did not result in optimal attendance. None of the SSH committee members attended the working group, but 22 committee members in SSH were invited. Seven SSH committee members, however, informed the organizers that they could not attend the meeting. Out of the 23

committee members in STEM that were invited, four attended the working group. One committee member informed the organizers that they could not attend the meeting.

The resistance can be manifested in the low attendance at the working group. Only a small minority of the invited participants attended, most of whom are already working with equality matters, by being in or working with the equality committee. Other participants could be described as being very positive towards gender equality matters and already interested in the gender practices in the evaluation and selection processes. Hence, the committee members that would benefit from discussing the construction of excellence and gender practices in the selection process did not attend. Which would be important, since the findings from task 7.1 and 7.2 revealed that there is a general resistance among the committee members to discuss gender and gender related topics and acknowledge that gender is an important factor in the selection process.

The learning points we have gained from planning and carrying out the working groups, that future working group leaders need to take into account, were the following:

- The participants were very interested and described the working group as practical and useful. Their comments indicate that there is need for a discussion on these matters in relation to the evaluation and selection processes.
- A working group, like this one, can be a successful tool to raise awareness on the construction of excellence and the gender practices involved in the evaluation and selection process. It is important to include the other academic schools.
- It is important to find ways to increase participation and increase the commitment from the committee members. This could be done by making the working group mandatory for all committee members and the mandate has to come from the top administration, such as the rector.
- All committee members and staff that take part in the selection of a candidate for a job opening at UI should receive an 'introduction package' when starting their work for the committees, in form of an on site training and/or educational material, also available online. Information on the construction of excellence and the gender practices in the evaluation and selection process, in this case the guidelines on the integration of equality dimensions in hiring and promotion, should be included in that introduction package. It is important that a person that has participated in all the phases of the selection process, such as the specialist from the Division of Science and Innovation, would be responsible for informing newcomers on these matters.
- It is important that there is one person, such as the specialist from the Division of Science and Innovation, is responsible for ensuring that 'the guidelines on the integration of equality dimensions in hiring and promotion' are used in the selection process.

2.4 CONCLUSION

It is very positive that the University of Iceland's Equality Committee is committed to make use of the outcomes of task 7.1 and 7.2 and the actions points that came out of the working groups to construct the guidelines on the integration of equality dimensions in

hiring and promotion, as required by the University of Iceland Equal Rights Policy 2013-2017.

A working group, like this one, can be a feasible instrument to raise and increase awareness on the construction of excellence and the gender practices involved in the evaluation and selection process. A working group or the gender equality training should be made mandatory for all evaluation and selection committee members in all five academic schools. During such seminar/course a specialist could introduce the guidelines on the integration of equality dimensions in hiring and promotion and train the committee members on applying it in the evaluation and selection process

3. ITALY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

The goal of this report is to describe and reflect on the implementation of two reflexive working groups with committee members performed in the two GARCIA beneficiary departments – the **Department of Sociology and Social Research (DSRS)** and at the **Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science (DISI)** – at the University of Trento (UNITN).

The two working groups were conducted by external consultants, three for the DISI and two for the DSRS, and different strategies were implemented in the two departments in order to involve the academic staff.

In both departments it was the first time that this type of action was implemented.

The aim of both reflexive working groups was to reflect on/to analyse: a) the evaluation criteria and practices adopted in selection/recruitment processes of researchers, b) which mechanisms can foster the reproduction of gender inequalities, gender biases and disparities starting from the early stages of the academic career, c) the mechanisms, events, features which can trigger the accumulation of disadvantages in career development in academia.

The report consists of two parts: the set-up, and the evaluation of each working groups.

Before moving to the presentation of the reflexive working groups, we will provide a brief description of the specific context of UNITN and of the two GARCIA beneficiary departments considering gender unbalance along the career ladder and selection processes at the early career stages.

UNITN is one of the Italian universities with the lowest presence of women among its research and academic staff. In 2014, the proportion of women in the university's entire academic staff (full, associate and assistant professors, postdocs) was 29.7%, while the Italian average was 40.5%. Both the Garcia beneficiary departments are strongly unbalanced in terms of sex distribution along the academic ladder. The lack of women is particularly visible among the top positions: at the DISI there are no female full professors while at the DSRS they were only 2 at the end of 2015. Moreover, in both cases, the level of feminization of the academic staff is systematically lower than the national average of the related academic fields (Ferri et al. 2016).

Considering the target population of the GARCIA project, the incidence of fixed-term assistant professors and postdocs at UNITN reached 42.6% of UNITN academic and research staff, which is about 7 percentage points higher than the Italian average. In the case of DISI the incidence of fixed term researchers exceeds 60% while in the DSRS these positions represent overall 35.5% of the department scientific staff.

The majority of fixed-term researchers (at national, local and department level) are research fellows (85%). Postdoctoral research fellows are grant-holders financed by external funds. The selection process of the postdoctoral research fellow grants is managed at the department level by a commission of three members, whose president is the holder of the research funding. Between 2010 and 2013, at the DISI were open 90 calls for postdoc positions and only in 1 case out of 4 it was appointed a female researcher.

In the case of the DSRS, out of 17 positions opened between 2010 and 2013, in 8 cases was appointed a female researcher.

Differently by postdocs, fixed term assistant professors are public servants, and the availability of these positions depends from the turnover rules fixed at national level and from the number of retirements within the permanent academic staff. In regard to their selection process, the Committee is composed of three full or associate professors and various evaluation phases are envisaged: a pre-selection (consisting in comparative evaluation of qualifications, CV, and three reference letters); the advice of three external referees appointed by the University Recruitment Committee; admission to the next phase of no fewer than six candidates. Then, a public discussion of the scientific qualifications with the Committee is foreseen. At the end of this phase, the Committee selects the candidates suitable for the appointment. The department board then deliberates on the candidate who will be appointed to the post, according to the Committee's evaluation. Between 2010 and 2013, 6 selections for fixed term assistant professors (without tenure-track) were opened at the DSRS, while only 2 were carried out at the DISI. At the DSRS, only 3 out of 18 professors who took part to the 7 selection committees were women, and only in one case the committee chair was a woman. In the case of DISI no women were included in the selection committee for fixed term assistant professors. At the end of these selection processes, 3 male and 4 female researchers were appointed at the DSRS, while 1 male and 1 female researchers were appointed at the DISI.

3.2 SET UP OF THE TASK

The goal of this action was to change the gender practices in recruitment, selection and evaluation processes in universities and research institutes. Organising reflexive working groups with committee members and other key players has the goal to promote a climate that decreases gender bias in evaluation moments but also to understand the mechanisms that usually lead this practices. The main policy of the action, indeed, was to raise awareness that evaluation criteria are not objectified truths, and that evaluators' conceptions of criteria can differ and could lead to disadvantage women.

Given the wide differences between the two departments in terms of gender composition, career development chances, research networks, level of internationalization (see: Bozzon et al. 2015; Murgia et al. 2016; Peroni, et al. 2015), two different workshops were organised with potential committee members in the two Garcia beneficiary departments at UNITN:

- 1) The first involved associate and full professors from the DISI and STEM disciplines and it took place on May 24th, 2016.
- 2) The second involved associate and full professors from the DSRS and it took place on June the 8th, 2016.

In the next paragraphs we will detail the set-up process of the two workshops.

3.2.1 STEM department (DISI)

In the case of the DISI, we decided to create a learning environment by organising a reflexive working group with committee members and other key players from an

international environment. We decided to do so due to the global context in which the department operates: it was in fact important for us to involve the professors of the department and, at the same time, to place the discussion in consideration to the international job market dynamics. For this reason, the workshop took place during COOP 2016 - XII International Conference on the Design of Cooperative Systems (<http://www.coop2016.unitn.it/>) – held in Trento between May 22th and May 28th 2016.

A free attendance workshop at COOP 2016 - XII International Conference on the Design of Cooperative Systems (<http://www.coop2016.unitn.it/>)

This workshop explores the precarization of work in academia and its intersections with the gender dimensions, a growing phenomenon in the last decade, with significant consequences in terms of intellectual development, continuity of streams of thinking and researchers' wellbeing.

The session will involve professors of the University of Trento and the COOP community in order to identify the criteria that are used to recruit Assistant Professors and to question them on the basis of the changing landscape of precarization, with particular attention to the gender dimension. The goal will be to identify actual criteria adopted in the recruitment process and to suggest alternatives which might have a positive impact on the situation.

Figure 3.1. Screenshot of the description of the GARCIA session within the COOP conference

During the conference we decided to place three different moments: the reflexive working groups with committee members, the workshop for prospective applicants and a third session in order to present all the results to the whole audience of the conference (more than 60 people belonging to the DISI department and the COOP conference attendees) during the plenary discussion.

COOP is one of the key European conferences on Cooperative Systems, Computer Supported Cooperative Work (CSCW) and Collaborative Computing and it is affiliated to EUSSET – the European Society for Socially Embedded Technologies. COOP 2016 was the twelfth edition of this biennial conference and took place for the first time in Trento, Italy, organised by the DISI and the Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK). The COOP conferences promote the idea that cooperative systems design requires a deep understanding of collective activities, involving both artefacts and social practices, within a context. This year, the programme intended to open up to the topic of collaborative design, with a special emphasis on “Making together”. In our opinion it was a great opportunity to involve the DISI community, in such an open environment, with an intimate setting, facilitating in-depth discussion and feedback in a multi-disciplinary community. The workshop we hosted, thus, was named “Making academic careers together. Recruitment, precariousness and gender” (<https://www.eventbrite.it/e/making-academic-careers-together-recruitment-and-precariousness-morning-session-registration-23419465251>).

The workshop main aim was to explore the precarization of work in academia and its intersections with the gender dimensions. We wanted to analyse its significant consequences in terms of intellectual development, continuity of streams of thinking and

researchers' wellbeing. Moreover, we wanted to discuss different perceptions of excellence, highlighting the existing gaps between formal criteria and criteria applied in actual decision making.

The session involved professors of the University of Trento and of the COOP community in order to identify the criteria that are used to recruit assistant professors and to question them. The target included committee chairs and members (academics who had been or could be potentially part of selection committees for early career researchers) from UNITN but also from the other universities in Ireland, Denmark, and Finland. They were 3 women and 2 men, all full professors. Moreover, several people from the GARCIA project, belonging both the DISI and the DSRS departments participated to the event.

The facilitators who led the workshop were:

Bianca Elzenbaumer holds a PhD in Design from Goldsmiths, University of London. She currently works as a Research Fellow at Leeds College of Art. In her practice-led doctoral thesis she explored precarious working conditions in the cultural industries. Since 2015, together with Fabio Franz, she has been running nomadic Precarity Pilot (www.precaritypilot.net) workshops throughout Europe in order to generate ideas for inventive yet feasible actions against precarization.

Fabio Franz is a PhD candidate at the Sheffield School of Architecture. His practice-led research focuses on the role of design in making of commons and community economies. Since 2005, he has been working together with Bianca Elzenbaumer as the design research practice Brave New Alps (www.brave-new-alps.com).

Maurizio Teli holds a PhD in Sociology and Social Research from the University of Trento. He is now Research Assistant Professor at the Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute, after holding the position of Research Fellow at the Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science at the University of Trento. In his research, he investigates the political intersections between the social sciences and the participatory design of digital technologies.

The workshop facilitators opened the session with an icebreaking question: "What would you never tell someone applying to be an assistant professor?". From this point the discussion was opened and we got many different feedbacks and point of views, from a gender perspective, but also influenced from personal experiences and their own institution' practices. The participants mostly worked in group to identify criteria for selecting assistant professors. The underlying questions we suggested as possible guidelines of the discussion were:

- What are official criteria in your institution for the appointment of assistant professor?
- What is influencing how strictly these criteria are applied?
- Have selection criteria been changed in the last decade?
- What is influencing the application of the official criteria?
- What does it take to be able to fulfil these criteria - for instance in terms of work generated and networks someone is part of?
- According to what criteria have you been selected?

- How many people did you select in the past 5 years? How many of them were male, how many female?
- What dilemmas do you encounter during the selection process?

The main purpose was to identify actual criteria adopted in the recruitment process in their own story and institution.

Figure 3.2. Picture taken during the workshop

Finally, they had to reconstruct all the given input through the lens of two last questions:

- What is the impact of the identified aspects from a gender perspective?
- How can the identified aspects be changed in order to allow for more inclusiveness?

With these closing questions, our goal was – starting from the criteria adopted in the recruitment process – to suggest alternatives, relevant and salient in the field of the STEM, which might have a positive impact on the situation.

The discussion was fluid and extremely participated, in particular because the women full professors who were attending the workshop, were the only female full professors in their own departments. Starting from their personal experiences, especially comparing them with the ones of their male colleagues, it was discussed how strongly gender influences the academic career of individuals.

In particular, the topics we discussed the most were the concept of “excellence” and how to relate the personal life to the needs coming from the requirements related to this opaque concept, all in the key of a gender perspective.

Figure 3.3. Poster realised during the workshop that re-cluster the inputs of the participants.

The main areas of discussion, thus, were:

- Excellence
- Networking
- Academia as a highly competitive environment

Following, the input that came out of the working group were translated in action points and recommendations. The discussion between the participants and the facilitators became more like a friendly conversation and the recommendations were given more as advices for people applying for an associate professor position, particularly targeted for female researchers. The aim of the full professors that were participating was to offer an alternative perspective and a set of advices – able to take into consideration gender biases – that could help in developing early career researcher's curriculum and their working trajectory in order to have more chances in applying for an assistant professor position and, more in general, to get a (more) stable position in academia.

Figure 3.4. Poster realised during the workshop with the participant's inputs about the actual situation and possible recommendations.

We decided to summarize the discussion in a *vademecum*, as it was elaborated during the workshop, that could be helpful for future committee members.

In your work as member of a committee for recruiting an assistant professor, in order to avoid discriminations and to acknowledge gender differences in the applications, you should always remember to:

- Evaluate the research achievements, but also the research potentials. It is difficult to build a consistent research activity in case postdocs have to move from project to project in order to get funds.
- Being aware of invisible work: sometimes, indeed, early career researchers – and especially women - may face under recognition of their work. Ask also what is not “on the paper” and do not limit your evaluation to what is in the CV
- Evaluate collaborative works: independence is extremely important, but it does not mean working alone
- In the recruitment process you will need to:
 - Let the applicants know who is doing the evaluation
 - Consider the context in which the applicants worked in the past
 - Institutional (researchers can stay long time in a postdoc position due to lack of vacancies)

- Needs at the time (what the research group they were working with required: publishing, fundraising..)
- Reject is part of the game but you will still have to encourage the applicants and to provide them useful feedbacks
- Be aware of the pressure coming from the fulfilment of the hard requirements. Most of the times, these requirements are not about the quality but about the quantity and the indexes. Keep in mind that numbers are not “the only truth”.
- Take into consideration that everyone should have the opportunity to dedicate time to their private and family life.

The last question of the workshop, then, was “Who is going to change the academic system?”. The challenge behind this question was to understand who, if not even affirmed full professors do it, could scatter discriminatory mechanisms played in academia. The question remained unsolved due to the limited time and because it was decided to propose it as an object of discussion in the plenary session.

Thus, the question was resubmitted in the dedicated time slot during the final plenary session to discuss about gender biases in the construction of excellence and in the recruitment procedures. This session of restitution was extremely helpful because we had the chance to present the outputs of the workshop to a larger audience, namely all the COOP participants (more than 60 people among the DISI department staff and the conference attendees). Our results had been welcomed with lively interest from the audience, that responded with questions and other very interesting inputs about the concept of excellence and visibility in academia.

During the restitution we discussed also the outcomes of a second workshop that took place in the afternoon of the same day (<https://www.eventbrite.it/e/biglietti-making-academic-careers-together-recruitment-precariousness-and-gender-afternoon-session-23420158324>) conducted with PhDs, post docs and early career researchers of the DISI department. In the second workshops, they worked on the outputs of the committee member’s one and tried to elaborate them further. The results are presented and discussed in the dedicated GARCIA report.

All the contributions – elaborated in the two sessions with committee members and with early career researchers, as well as in the discussion we had in the plenary session – were summarized by the GARCIA team and the facilitators of the workshop, and merged into a “Manifesto for the future of precarious post-docs and PhD students”. Due to the enthusiastic reaction in the plenary session, it had been decided to graphically re-elaborate the document to disseminate it among UNITN academic community but also outside our institution, in order to raise awareness among committee members on the gender practices and the problematics related to the access to tenure positions. For this reason, we decided to create a dedicated webpage that is now under construction but

that has been already discussed and agreed among the GARCIA team and UNITN offices in charge of the institutional web pages.

3.2.2 SSH department (DSRS)

The reflexive working group with committee members at the DSRS was titled “Come valorizzare i talenti nella ricerca?” (How can we promote talents in research?) and it was promoted both on the DSRS website and by an invitation email sent to the department staff by Mario Diani – Head of DSRS – Barbara Poggio – vice Rector for equality and diversity at UNITN – and Alessia Donà – delegate for equal opportunities at DSRS. We officially invited to the event all the full and associate professors of the Department.

Moreover, in order to foster the participation of the department staff, an informal promotion was conducted by two key members of the Garcia project, who occupy strategic position at the department and university level: Carlo Buzzi, who was head of the Department in the past and (until this Spring) was member of the University Senate; and Barbara Poggio, vice Rector for equality and diversity.

Below the invitation sent by email to all the associate and full professors.

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI TRENTO
DIPARTIMENTO DI SOCIOLOGIA E RICERCA SOCIALE

garcia
Seminari e workshop
per la valorizzazione
della ricerca scientifica

Supporto
per il Programma
della European Union

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI TRENTO
Uffici di
uguaglianza e
diversità

8 Giugno 2016, 14:30
Sala Riunioni – Secondo piano, Via Verdi 26 Trento

**Come valorizzare i talenti nella
ricerca scientifica**

Relatore:
Antonio Chiesi

Moderata:
Daniela Falcinelli

Introduce:
Barbara Poggio

Workshop rivolto a professori e professoressse associati/e e ordinari/e del Dipartimento di Sociologia e Ricerca Sociale.

Segreteria Dipartimento - Via Verdi, 26 - 38122 Trento, Italy - Tel. +39 0461/281322, Fax +39 0461/281458 segreteria.srs@unitn.it

Figure 3.5. Invitation sent by email to all the associate and full professors

The date and the moderators of the event were chosen after a careful analysis of the department needs and commitments (it was a period in which all the students' examinations were scheduled and then it was crucial to avoid any possible overlapping).

Firstly, we fixed the working group in concomitance with other department institutional activities (the Department Board). In this way we guaranteed the presence in Trento of the vast majority of the department members. At the reflexive working group took part 14 professors (4 females and 10 males) out of 37 invited full and associate professors of the DSRS.

The moderators of the reflexive working group were chosen on the basis of two criteria: 1) a consolidated experience in managing structural change projects and actions in academia, 2) and their previous relations with the DSRS. These were the main reasons why we decided to ask to conduct the workshop to Daniela Falcinelli and Antonio Maria Chiesi.

Daniela Falcinelli is Adjunct Professor of Equal Opportunities and Scientific Careers. She is currently coordinating the research centre "GENDERS – Gender & Equality in Research and Science" and the research project STAGES "Structural Transformation to Achieve Gender Equality in Science" at the University of Milan. She has a long-lasting and consolidated experience in the development and implementation of structural change project and on gender-equality issues in academia. She coordinated the European project PRAGES "Practising Gender Equality in Science" (7FP, 2008-2009), and the European project WHIST "Women's careers Hitting the Target in Scientific and Technological research (7FP, 2009-2011) at the University of Milan.

Antonio Maria Chiesi is full professor of Sociology and currently head of the Department of Social Science at the University of Milan, and member of the research projects STAGES, WHIST and PRAGES. He was part of the DSRS until 2005. In the early 2000 he was head of the DSRS for three years, so he has a privilege knowledge of the department dynamics and of the department permanent academic staff.

The reflexive working group was organised as a roundtable.

After a short presentation of the GARCIA project made by Barbara Poggio, the two facilitators introduced themselves, described their competences on gender inequalities and gender policies in academia, their long-lasting experience in structural change projects (STAGES, PRAGES, and WHIST) focusing on the relevance of the knowledges and practices accumulated over time through these research activities.

They problematized three main topics:

- Gender inequalities, gender biases and stereotypes in academic career development, with a focus on how the disadvantages' accumulation works in reproducing gender gaps.
- The policies implemented at the organisational level able to foster gender equality in science, with a focus on the conditions that allow to activate a virtuous (cultural) change, and the role of the governance's commitment.
- The definition of scientific excellence and its criteria from the point of view of who is part of a specific field of science.

The debate with the participants was driven by two key issues:

- How they interpret gender asymmetries in career development in their department starting from a comment to the gender distribution across academic positions at the DSRS and the “scissor diagram” of the University of Trento (Figure1). How they define scientific excellence and which criteria allow to identify excellent researchers in their research field.

Figure 3.6. Slides used for the discussion at the DSRS

The discussion was quite lively even if led mainly by five professors (four men and one woman) and it focused on the following themes:

- The structural factors which can influence the gender composition of the department and the difficulties of women career advancement: gender horizontal and vertical segregation and gap in scientific production were the most problematized factors.
- The assumptions behind gender equality promotion/policies and their ambivalent relation with scientific quality. A part of the research staff openly considers scientific quality the most important aim of the academic job and interprets gender equality in SSH disciplines as a secondary objective that could be (slowly) reached in the future through an open competition based on scientific productivity.
- The evaluation of policies based on women quotas or on gender economic incentives and their ambivalent results in terms of gender equality in the short and in the long run. Some professors stressed the risk that an unappropriated application of these policies could devalue and delegitimize women scientific activities, and untie the female presence in the academic system and the women career advancement from their scientific productivity, skills, competences, and knowledges. On the other hand, other participants were concerned about the difficulties to manage policies/actions that produce limited or null effects in the short-run but that could trigger a virtuous accumulation process visible only in the long-run.
- The lack of women in top positions and its consequences on the efforts to guarantee gender equality in institutional boards and selection committees, which can congest the time schedule of the few women professors available affecting their scientific productivity.
- The need to pay attention to the department everyday life, to the schedule of department meetings, boards and etc., which significantly interfere with other crucial scientific activities (mainly publications) influencing women chances of career advancements.
- Welfare regimes and gender roles in society and their influence on work-life interferences and women career chances in academia.
- The role of gender stereotypes, unconscious biases and rational expectations in trigger gender disadvantages and the (re)production of gender inequalities.

Given to the time constrains of the working group (2 hours), it was difficult to deepen all the elements discussed. However, the discussion was useful to increase the awareness among professors on how gender differences can influence women careers and how criteria that are used to define “excellence” may operate in recruitment processes. Indeed, one of the main aims of the Garcia project was to increase the awareness of the existing gap between ideal representations and actual practices in the involved departments.

Several participants to the workshop, for instance, were impressed about the fact that gender differences are higher at the University of Trento in comparison to the Italian average. Since our university is at the top position at the national level, in fact, also the full and associate professors of the DSRS thought that the University of Trento has better performance also in terms of gender equality.

Moreover, an increased sensibility of potential evaluators could entail the introduction of a more comprehensive analysis of the applications, taking into consideration the socially embedded dimensions of excellence, in order to avoid gender biases in evaluation criteria.

At the end of the workshop, two action points or recommendations came out from the working group.

The first concerned the time schedules of the department/university institutional duties in order to guarantee the equal involvement of women and men in these situations, reducing the interference with private and family life. More precisely, the department should avoid to schedule institutional activities late in the afternoon.

The second is related to the efforts to pay more attention to small actions and practices which hide unconscious gender biases and can foster the accumulation of gender disadvantages in career development. The discussion during the working group focused mainly on gender biases connected to the involvement in administrative and devalued tasks experienced especially by women since the early career stages.

The commitment of all professors was not reached during the working group, because of the heterogeneous positions expressed by the participants. However, some positive feedbacks from a part of the participants were obtained when the contents of the working group focused on practices and actions which hide unconscious biases and their role in activating and reproduce gender disadvantages in career development.

3.3 EVALUATION OF THE TASK

This paragraph focuses on the evaluation of the two workshops. More precisely, we will consider the following four points: 1) what have worked when performing the working groups, 2) what challenges and resistances we encountered, 3) what learning points we gain from planning the working groups and 4) the specificity of UNITN context and what future action could be undertaken.

3.3.1 STEM department

During the workshop, the participants were really open to discuss all the issues emerged in the conversation, even the most controversial, and they were also open in admitting what is not working in the “academic game” in their research field. We have to consider that their perception has been built from their personal experience and the context they know, but they realised soon that the identified dynamics do not differ much from country to country.

The discussion in the group flowed easily, even if the attendees stated some very strong opinions on the state of art of the academic system. None of them tried to deny that gender practices in recruitment exist, in particular in the STEM disciplines, to the point that at the very beginning of the workshop one of them said:

“[...] gender become a discriminant of what is available to you in the different fields of research” (Female, Full Professor)

When the discussion moved to the topics of the requirements and the practice of “gaming the system” to maximise the professional escalation, the attendees were not saying those mechanisms proudly, but their attitude was more resigned to what the actual practices – in their opinion and from their personal experiences – are.

Possible elements that helped the good flow of the conversation were the heterogeneity of the participant’s backgrounds and the fact that they were colleagues in the international community. Moreover, having external facilitators of the workshop, may have helped to start the dialogue and discussion without concerns.

Another key ingredient for the good outcome of the workshop was the ability and the predisposition of the participants to use tools proper of the collaborative practices. Being all expert users of these techniques, due to their research interests, helped the fluid start of the discussion activities. This allowed the creation of concrete outcomes, even of direct and tangible recommendations.

During the workshop we did not have any specific resistance. The challenge, indeed, was to contain the flow of the discussion and to guide it to the point, focussing more on gender practices. In addition, we did not have many participants but this challenge actually turned into an opportunity because we had the possibility to focus more on the personal experiences. It gave to the group many fruitful inputs for the dialogue, involving all the participants and keeping their full attention until the end.

Moreover, also because the number of participants to the workshop was lower than what we expected, it was crucial to have a dedicated moment in the plenary session during the last day of the conference planned ahead. In this context, the fact that the professors who attended the GARCIA workshop felt involved also from a personal and biographical point of view had been a very important element also because during the plenary session they were able to stimulate their colleagues to be involved in a broader discussion. Indeed, in the restitution moment in the plenary session, where we were presenting the results of the workshop, people who participated felt that their personal stories contributed to create the “Manifesto for the future of precarious post-docs and PhD students”, elaborated on the basis of both the workshops realised with committee members and with early career researchers at the DISI.

The goal of the manifesto was to make visible that researchers are people with needs and early career researchers should not be invisible. In particular, from the contribution given by the full professors, there was a strong request to make the rules of the academic game clear to everyone. This is something that was agreed and shared from early career researchers to all the full professors who were there, even more strongly by the female professors who had to experience these kind of challenges in their professional paths.

We received many positive feedbacks on the work done during that day. All the professors and young researchers who were at the restitution moment asked for more information, in particular about how they could disseminate the manifesto. For this reason, we decided to create a dedicated webpage, in order to maximise the visibility of the contribution elaborated during the workshop and to share it as much as possible. More details about this webpage are available on the Garcia report focused on the workshops realised with early career researchers.

From the discussions it appeared that the specific point that could be valid for our institution (UNITN), are shared also among many others context and academics. Our main purpose, which future working group leaders may take into account, is spreading awareness of gender practices and how to counter those practices in the evaluation of excellence. The manifesto and the guidelines emerged from the workshops will be disseminated to enlighten gender practices in evaluating excellence in the university.

3.3.2 SSH department

In the process of organising the working group at the DSRS, the most strategic choice concerned the selection of the two external facilitators. In fact, we deliberately decided to entrust the management of the working group to two experts with a wide competence on gender asymmetries in academia and in conducting structural change projects, but also persons well-known and valued within the DSRS community. More precisely the presence of a man who currently is head of the Department of Sociology at the University of Milan and who was member of the DSRS until 2005 fostered the participation of associate and full professors of the department, and helped to legitimize the topics discussed during the workshop.

This strategic choice, together with the informal networking conducted by two key members of the GARCIA team in Trento (Carlo Buzzi and Barbara Poggio), produced a positive effect and the formal commitment of department staff: more than one third of the invited associate and full professors took part to the working group. Interestingly, all the department research units were represented and the participants were quite heterogeneous in terms of research interests and approaches.

The way we structured the discussion on previous results and experiences cumulated in other structural changes projects permitted to sparked an interesting discussion and to address the issue of gender inequalities in academic careers.

The main challenge we faced was to shift the debate from a theoretical level and a reflexive analysis to the commitment in implementing concrete actions aimed to sustain gender equality since the very beginning of the academic career. Moreover, the debate was led mainly by five persons, and the time constraints limited the possibility to involve all the participants in the discussion. However, a longest meeting would have discouraged the participation of the invited professors without a strong interest on gender equality issues.

The reactions of participants can be polarized in two main groups:

The first group, the most visible one, comprises professors who reacted to gender equality issues using topics based on their research experience. With this group, the debate remained on a theoretical ground.

The second group comprises department members who have never reflected before the workshop on: 1) the gender gap in the academic staff of the department and the university where they are working in, 2) and how implicit codes and actions and unconscious biases affect also their working environment. In this case the main difficulty was to manage their frustration – as experts in social sciences – of not being immune from well-known mechanisms that feed the reproduction of social inequalities. In this case, the

working group allowed to foster a self-reflexion about gender discriminating processes which operate at the decision-making levels at the DSRS and UNITN.

Planning and performing a working group with professors from the department where is employed most part of the GARCIA research group in Trento were the most challenging action implemented during the project for different reasons.

Firstly, because it meant to involve in the reflexive working groups experts in social sciences who often use reflexive methods and techniques in their scientific job, and/or often have a previous consolidated position/opinion about the themes discussed during the working group. In such situation, it was very difficult to introduce in the discussion paradoxical and counter-intuitive examples, or to use other ice-breaking strategies which usually facilitate the discussion among researches from the STEM disciplines.

Secondly, since one of the main aim was to raise awareness about gender asymmetries in career development, it was crucial to find a way to involve in the working group people with heterogeneous positions and who do not explicitly use a gender-sensitive approach in their scientific activities. In this case, the presence of an estimated (male) ex-member of the DSRS was crucial to legitimise the topics developed during the event and to obtain the participation of professors with other approaches not primarily interested in gender issues. This aim also constrained the duration of the working group: events lasting more than two hours usually attract only people with a strong commitment on gender issues.

Thirdly, since both facilitators and participants share the same scientific community, which overcome the organisational boards of the department, some unexpected power dynamics – independent from the aims of the working group – were difficult to be avoided and managed. In this sense, in the future, it could be useful to involve in the working group an external and/or international facilitator with no interests in the Italian academic dynamics.

3.4 CONCLUSION

In organising the two working groups in the two GARCIA beneficiary departments at UNITN, we followed two completely different strategies.

In the case of the DISI, we chose three facilitators with a previous experience in conducting reflexive working groups in STEM environments, and with competences in gender and precariousness. Moreover, we decided to place the execution of the working group within the international framework of the COOP conference. This choice fostered the participation of some full professors from the DISI department, but also from other European universities. Given the high turnover of temporary researchers and their limited chances of obtaining a stabilization within the DISI and in the Italian context, it is important to maintain an international horizon in raising awareness on gender bias in career development and excellence criteria with the DISI academic staff.

In the case of the DSRS, our main concern was to obtain the participation to the workshop of department members from the different research units, independently by their scientific position on gender issues. The decision to entrust the management of this action to a well-known and appraised full professor who was head of the DSRS in the early

2000 allowed to obtain a consistent formal commitment from the department staff. In fact, 14 professors from different research groups took part to the workshop.

In both departments, the reflexive working group created an open space to reflect upon the processes that feed gender asymmetries in academia and open up the possibility for all participants to give their contributions and inputs to the discussion. However, the final outcomes of the working groups strongly differ between the two contexts.

In the case of the DISI we reached a strong commitment among the participants during the workshop. Starting from their personal experience in selection processes, they openly discussed of the invisible rules of the academic game and the gender biases experienced in their environment. Their thoughts and experiences contributed to the contents included in the manifesto presented in the plenary session of the COOP Conference. This document was shared after the conference at UNITN and international level through a dedicated website.

In the case of the DSRS we faced a more challenging environment characterised by more polarized positions within the academic staff in relation to gender issues in academic careers. Moreover, the debate was developed on a more sophisticated level and participants spoke mainly starting from their scientific/research experiences. Facilitators faced strong resistances in shifting the focus of the workshop on organisational practices, individual actions and personal experiences. However, a part of the audience showed a genuine interest in the reflection on issues connected to the reproduction of unconscious biases and gender stereotypes in academic organisations and their role in inhibit the participation of women in selection processes or their involvement in secondary and devalued tasks.

In this context, as a result of the Garcia project activities and of the actions implemented by the vice Rector for equality and diversity of the University of Trento, in the last calls for postdoctoral fellowships at the DSRS, the following sentence was added to the announcement of selection with the aim to make explicit the university commitment in gender equality:

“The University of Trento is an equal opportunity employer and positively encourages applications from people in under-represented groups”.

GARCIA’s most original contribution concerns the focus on early stages of the academic career, most concerned by employment instability and, foremost, by detrimental effects of academia and science as “greedy institutions”, at the basis of the leaky pipeline phenomenon. Therefore, the implementation of the actions regarding recruitment and selection processes from lower grades of academia (D and C levels), and the activities aiming at awareness-raising of gendered subtexts in the evaluation of “excellence”, has been crucial.

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4. THE NETHERLANDS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The goal of this report is to describe and reflect on the execution of WP7 task 7.3 “Reflexive working groups with committee members”. The report consists of two parts: the set-up of the working groups and the evaluations. The accumulation of reports from all GARCIA beneficiaries will be used to build a tool for universities and research institutes to bring awareness to selection committee members on the construction of excellence, the practice of appointment procedures for early career academics, and the gender dimension (Deliverable 7.3 and 7.4: Format tool reflexive working groups).

The main objective of the GARCIA reflexive working groups was to discuss hiring and selection of early career scholars with committee members in SSH and STEM. The first aim was to disseminate results of the GARCIA WP7 work package. Specifically, the goal was to discuss the discrepancy between ‘formal’ criteria often displayed in job advertisement texts, and the actual criteria deployed when a candidate is selected. The second aim was to bring an understanding as to how gender plays or may play a role in the recruitment and selection processes in which they take part. For instance, candidates are often judged on their teaching evaluations by committees, but research has shown that women are evaluated worse by students than men. This may well have gendered implications for which person committee members appoint. The third aim was to together with the participants reconsider the criteria and selection processes to see how these could become gender neutral, and come up with recommendations and action points to counter gendered selection procedures.

Our aim was to perform two reflexive working groups, one in each institute, i.e. SSH and STEM. These had the target group of all senior academic staff who were or would be members of selection committees of early career scholars. Due to difficulties in aligning agendas of target group members, the reflexive working group at the SSH could not be organized before September 2016 (which is after the deadline of this report). In addition, with approval of the faculty dean the reflexive working groups planned to be organized for the STEM were considered beneficial for the whole Faculty of Science (STEM) and were thus organized for the whole faculty instead only one institute within STEM.

Two reflexive working groups were planned at STEM shortly after each other, on Thursday 2 June 2016 and Monday 6 June 2016. They were organized in consultation with the secretary of the STEM institute regarding practical arrangements. Invitations were written by the GARCIA researchers - in consultation with the STEM head of director for the STEM - and then sent out to the senior staff through the dean’s secretary.

Within SSH, postdocs are not a standard position and the numbers are limited. Some are hired informally, others formally and yet others on personal grants. Assistant professors are most often hired through the networks of professors, though formal procedures are usually in place. Within STEM, postdocs are for the large part hired informally or enter the institute on personal grants. Assistant professors are hired through formal procedures.

Similar working groups do not exist yet within the university. However, in the framework of the new diversity programme of the university, the central personnel department has asked the GARCIA project leaders to set up and facilitate similar working

groups university-wide. The GARCIA working groups function as a pilot and blueprint for these working groups.

4.2 SET UP OF THE TASK

Fourteen STEM committee members registered for the working group of 2 June, among which eight women and six men. In total, fourteen committee members actually participated, among which seven women and seven men. For the working group of 6 June, ten committee members registered, among which five women and five men. In total, nine committee members actually participated: five women and four men.

The working group was set up as follows. First, the working group leaders introduced themselves and the GARCIA project. An introductory round was done for the participants to know each other and for the working group leaders to make an inventory of what each participant wanted to learn or discuss during the working group, and what they saw as the biggest challenges for gender neutral recruiting. The topics STEM participants mentioned were:

- Generally: to learn about gender biases
- What are ways to recognize implicit biases and how to counter/deal/change them?
- To become aware of our own biases
- How to advise female colleagues in their career?
- Improve the number of women within the faculty

Then the working group leaders presented some gender statistics in academia to show the necessity of gender-focused action research as well as the need for committee members to reflect on their own recruitment and selection practices.

The working group leaders presented the criteria for recruitment and selection of an assistant professor to show the formally described criteria usually found in job advertisements for that position within the STEM. They commented that there is a hierarchy of importance among this list of criteria. They explained which were actually the key criteria found in the GARCIA research and how the composition of the selection committee impacts those criteria. The informal recruitment of postdocs as found in the GARCIA research was also discussed.

Then gender was brought into the working group. The working group leaders elaborated on what gender and gender inequality in academia are. They explained that 'quality' and 'meritocracy' are not objective and gender neutral concepts, but are gender biased and power-laden. They backed these statements up using previous research.

Next, the working group went into the topic of informal recruitment, which is an important element of both postdoc and assistant professor recruitment. The working group leaders explained how this is also gendered: the similar-to-me effect and differential network outcomes were discussed, among other aspects.

Interview dynamics were the next topics. The goal was to help participants be aware of and reflect on their role in the interviews and how these may impact their selection decisions.

After these topics, the working group leaders elaborated on possibilities for change: how can selection committees and procedures be arranged so that the eventual selection of

early career researchers is truly done on the basis of meritocratic grounds and gender neutral criteria? Participants came up with several suggestions:

- A test to see if participants are suitable for committees after attending the workshop
- A critical evaluation of the selection process
- Involvement of the faculty dean
- Working together with HR
- The chair of the committee should have a powerful position

Whether there is commitment among key players to use these suggestions is difficult to assess. The evaluations (see 3.1) suggest there is commitment. The existence of the Gender and Diversity committee within the faculty and different departments (e.g. STEM) indicate to a certain commitment. However, some participants say it is hard to change things when the faculty policy is not changed. It remains difficult to ‘walk the talk’; the urgency within the faculty is insufficiently felt.

The working group ended with some suggestions made by the working group leaders to take home, such as “Construct criteria carefully, question assumptions” and “Start scouting, supporting and sponsoring talented, ambitious women”.

Throughout the working group, plenty of questions (Q) were asked and remarks (R) were made:

- R: Tell your colleagues about the workshop.
- Q: Why is the workshop not mandatory for all staff?
- R: There are no postdocs in the graph.
- Q: [postdocs] Is that the first step in the leaky pipeline?
- R: [recruitment and selection criteria: what do we need?]:
 - Quality of past performance in relation to peer group.
 - Outstanding candidates
 - To be first author, which shows taking initiative
 - Good references
 - 1) Funding, 2) Funding, and 3) Funding
 - Strong publications
 - Attracting new tenure trackers
 - Teamworker; having a network
 - Maybe potential leadership
- R/Q: [with regard to recruitment and selection criteria] Are we talking about tenure trackers of assistant professors? Otherwise we talk on two different levels.
 - R: You’re not selected to be a great teacher.
 - R: Funding covers it all.
 - R: You want the best.
- R: Good candidates were rejected because they did not fit
- R: There is a difference in the purpose of the [vacancy] text and what is decided in interviews. (below surface of the iceberg)
- R: [with regard to “outsourcing selection to funding organizations] This is very true.

- R: Same for journals. [R: but shortage in funding, not a shortage in journals].
 - R: In the end a very good project is not funded
- R: The best PhDs go searching for a postdoc position: you want those PhDs who actively search.
- R: Women applicants are giving reserved answers; men are more confident.
- Q: How can we remedy?
- R: [pregnant women/women on pregnancy leave] are not out of the world.
 - R: Also young fathers.
- R/Q: It is about being critical to yourself, isn't it?
- R: [example that supervisor/manager did not ask if woman on pregnancy leave would like to go to a conference] It was my decision to go to the conference or not.
 - R: That has something to do with hierarchy: you are reluctant to send an email due to the pressure to decline.
 - R: You should mention it, talk about it, discuss before you(r) leave.
- R: I strive for a selection committee with 50% men and 50% women.
 - R: Do not talk about the 50/50; women want to be invited as speakers for their quality.
 - R: They do not want to be the 'excuustruus'
 - R: Same for men.
 - Q: Can you extrapolate that to selection committees? How do you tackle that?
- R: In my time, when I was recruited, gender was not im frage; when women are now appointed there are always second thoughts.
- Q: Is it not something for HR? Shouldn't HR have a more active role in this?
 - R: [This should not be the responsibility of HR], but they should control that it happens.
- R: Help from all sides would help.
- R: We talked about the "don't rank [during selection process]" before
- Q: [with regard to the graph] Is it controlled for the time-factor?
- R: There are not so much/ not enough women around
- R: [with regard to slide recruitment and selection criteria] It is normal.
 - R: Nothing there about social skills
 - R: Teaching skills are always asked, but hardly taken into account
- R: There are definitely politics going on.
- R: [Influence of] faculty policy. The hiring committee advises, then the faculty overruled the decision of committee.
- R: [with regard to pregnancy leave] 18 months is not enough to have a child. 18 months is not enough for everything.
- R: [with regard to outsourcing selection to funding organizations] I agree, but universities let it happen.
- R: Age matters
- R: The criteria are more or less standard. It is the duty of the chair that all candidates are asked the same questions.

- R: [with regard to the topic ‘Basking in reflected glory’] No, I do not agree.
- R: [Women get remarks] You probably have really good changes [to get funding/grant] because you are a woman.
- R: I have heard about a research where proposals without names were evaluated and men were better evaluated than women. Men write bolder. [Nobody else heard of this research]
- R: [Call for] blind assessment
- R: [with regard to scouting] It is a really bad practice but it is happening.
- Q: Where can we find females?
- R/Q: That’s why the GARCIA team only consists of women?
- Q: Can we use special selection companies?
 - o R: University of Utrecht is using it. They found candidates they never thought off.
- Q: Are there things in criteria to attract women?
 - o R: I recently found out that females want to work 0.8 fte
 - o R: All my female PhD students work 0.8 fte.
- Q: I also heard if there are 8 criteria, when women have 6 they do not apply, when men have 4 they do apply. What can you do about that?
- Q: Could you circulate job advertisements which you think is good?
- R: The chair of the committee must be somebody who has reputation
 - o R: It helps if it is a man
- R: We have a rule on the committee that there should be a female of academic level
- Q: Why does the Netherlands does so bad in Europe? Child support is good; why is the Netherlands worse than other countries?
- Q: Is it thinkable to have an exam?

We finished the working group with handing out an evaluation form, which asked:

- *What are the most important insights you gained from the working group?*
- *How did you experience the presentation and facilitation of the working group? (Pleasant unpleasant, informal, formal, informative, etc.)*
- *What could be improved about the working group?*

We discuss the answers to these questions under **3. Evaluation of the task.**

4.3 EVALUATION OF THE TASK

What worked for you when planning and performing the working groups?

The secretaries were helpful in arranging a room and the lunch, which alleviated some of the work. The head of the STEM adapted the invitation written by the GARCIA team so as to be more appealing to his institute. He added that participation was expected.

What challenges and resistances have you come across when planning and performing the working groups? How did you overcome them (or not)?

No challenges were met during the planning of the working groups. During the performing of the working groups, there were a few challenges.

A first challenge was the opening speech of the faculty dean. The faculty dean opened both working groups with a brief speech (after which he left). In the first working group (2 June), he disclaimed the working group and the working group leaders by ‘making a joke’ that ‘this is not hard science’. During the second workshop (6 June) he rephrased this message by referring to the gamma background of the working group leaders and research project.

A second challenge was a missing slide during the first working group. The slide that mentioned all recruitment and selection criteria was missing by accident. To compensate for the missing slide, the workshop leaders asked the participants to name the criteria they think are important in recruiting and selecting postdocs and assistant professors. This turned out to be a very good way to reveal possible differences that already existed between the participants, and to instigate a discussion about this. During the second working group, the slide was shown. Instead of discussion, there seemed to be agreement with the criteria listed.

A third challenge was to deal with questions about background information, such as statistics on gender differences between European countries, or methods to come to certain statistical conclusions (triggered by slide 6 and 7). The presenters answered these questions briefly and tried not to get sidetracked too much.

What are the learning points you gained from planning and performing the working groups?

- Start well in advance with arranging organizational stuff: room, lunch, etc.
- Communicate with the dean or head of department about the text of the invitation. This will help to fine-tune the text and adjust it to the audience, which is often not in the direct environment of the working group leaders.
- Be sure to be in time in the room to have potential bugs fixed in time (e.g., when a projector/smartboard does not work)
- Keep the time schedule in mind but be flexible. Make sure there is enough room for questions and remarks. Do not tell at the start of the workshop that there is room at the end to raise questions but incorporate time for questions during the presentation of the research results.
- Make clear that the purpose of the workshop is to present our research findings in the particular department, not absolute do’s and don’ts. Point to people’s own agency to change their situation or the university system.
- Introduce a break, even if the participants indicate they do not need one. Participants do want a coffee/tea refill. If the workshop continues when all participants get their refill, it gets a bit disordered and participants are distracted, which is at the expense of the presentation.
- Consider the time/day on which the reflexive working group is organized. For example, Monday does not seem to be a good day for organizing a reflexive working group.

What feedback did you get from the participants?

Taken together, the participants gave the following answers to the evaluation form questions.

- *What are the most important insights you gained from the working group?*
 - Insight in criteria and considerations by selection committees

- Learning about how recruitment and selection mechanisms are influenced by (implicit) gender bias: “Gender bias is everywhere”
 - Awareness of (implicit) gender bias and its (potential) sources
 - That there is also bias in the scouting process and reference letters
 - The importance of briefing the selection committee
 - The importance of a proper, critical evaluation of the selection process
 - Awareness of different behaviours of men vs women in selection processes and the bias in the evaluation of these behaviours
 - That bias exist on both sides; i.e. both men and women are biased.
 - That there is a lack of a network to support women
 - To be critical and question “obvious assumptions”
 - Tips for vacancy texts
 - Tips on how to put together a selection committee
 - The importance of encouraging women to apply for jobs
 - “To promote more women myself”
 - The ambiguous role of HR: faculty staff emphasizes the role of HR, while there are ‘scientific reasons to do things “differently”’
- *How did you experience the presentation and facilitation of the working group?*
 - Open atmosphere; friendly and non-judgemental
 - Pleasant
 - Informal
 - Interactive
 - Informative
 - Nice; very good; great
 - Slightly too long
 - Beginning could be faster
 - Could have gone on for hours
 - Little room for discussion
 - Good dynamics of having two presenters
- *What could be improved about the working group?*
 - Generally: more practical, concrete and actual measures that can be taken and what actually can be done
 - Goal of the workshop leaders could be made more explicit at the beginning of the meeting: what is their goal with their arguments?
 - Duo presentation could be better coordinated
 - More interaction
 - More actual examples of what goes wrong in recruitment and selection; some statements can be taken in multiple ways
 - Introduction was a bit too long; get into gender issues faster
 - More male participation
 - Elaboration on the GARCIA project is less relevant and interesting

- If you are showing research results, you will get discussion about that. You need to show precisely the right data to convince the [STEM] audience
- The term ‘workshop’ raised practical expectations, while it was experienced as a information gathering to create awareness
- Discussion can be more efficient
- Let people practice with the interviews (role plays)
- Know your audience: this group did not need convincing, future groups probably will

What was specific for your context, which future working group leaders need to take into account?

- At the STEM/STEM, careers are built a bit different for the various sub-fields. You can prepare a general story, but attune your story according to those differences. Being first author on papers, for instance, is not a common criterion within astrophysics.
- At STEM the following step after finishing your PhD is becoming a postdoc. (At the SSH becoming a postdoc or applying for assistant professorships are both equal options).
- The ‘hidden’ norms within different faculties. For example, international experience is essential at STEM, but less explicit at the SSH.

4.4 CONCLUSION

At time of writing this report, we only conducted the working groups at STEM, so we cannot compare the two departments. This comparison is thus based on the two working groups that were organized for the Faculty of Science (STEM).

Compare the set-up and evaluation of the working groups in the two departments. What similarities and what differences did you encounter?

- Interactive atmosphere: in both working groups the participants needed little encouragement to ask their questions or make comments.
- Practical guidance needed: in both workshops the participants would have liked to see more practical discussion of how to cope with gender bias in recruitment and selection committees.
- During the first working group, a slide was missing by accident. This was the slide with the recruitment and selection criteria. To compensate for the missing slide, the workshop leaders asked the participants to name the criteria they think are important in recruiting and selecting postdocs and assistant professors. This turned out to be a very good way to reveal possible differences that already existed between the participants, and to instigate a discussion about this. During the second working group, the slide was shown. Instead of discussion, there seemed to be agreement with the criteria listed.

To what extent do you see the reflexive working groups as a feasible instrument to create or increase gender awareness among appointment committee members?

Overall, the reflexive working groups proved a feasible instrument to increase gender awareness and awareness for (implicit) bias in recruitment and selection processes. Although one participant indicated that the working group did not trigger the feeling of being biased, reactions of the other participants were positive and promising. The workshop would probably be even more helpful if there was more time to give more practical advice what actually can be done, and more practical and concrete examples of measures to be taken.

Yet, these participants voluntarily registered and attended the working group. Some of the participants were already involved in Gender & Diversity committees within their faculty or department, and therefore are aware of the gender problem, or at least to a certain extent. It is difficult to say how a reflexive working group would look like and how the dynamics will be with a group of participants that are forced to participate (due to upcoming rule at the STEM that selection committee members are obliged to follow the working groups, otherwise they are not allowed on selection committees).

What were the general action points and recommendations in the two departments to counter gender inequality in recruitment and selection decisions?

The following suggestions were made during the workshops by participants:

- A test to see if participants are suitable for committees after attending the workshop
- A critical evaluation of the selection process
- Involvement of the faculty dean
- Working together with HR
- The chair of the committee should have a powerful position

5. SLOVENIA

5.1 INTRODUCTION

The reflexive working group has been established at the Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (ZRC SAZU, SSH). Its members are from the SSH and STEM institutions that are situated at the Research centre. The invitation into the reflexive working group was also sent to the professors and researchers from the STEM test unit, which is the Department of Agronomy of the Biotechnical Faculty (BF). Unfortunately, nobody from the BF responded to the invitation. Therefore, the workshop was organised only at ZRC SAZU.

The members of the reflexive groups are the Heads of the institutes and the leaders of the management union. It should be noted that employment policies of ZRC SAZU (“Guidelines on organisation and systematisation of working positions”) have not provided for an official committee for the recruitment and selection procedure for the already employed Research Assistant and Research Fellow, since these positions fall under the promotion system and there is no need for a public announcement of the vacant position. However, in the cases when a recruitment and selection process for a new job opening is needed (because of a new research project), the eighteen institutions that form ZRC SAZU have internal criteria for recruitment and selection. In the past, known candidates were usually accepted. Often they had already worked in the institutions under a temporary contract and gained an opportunity through a new project to extend the contract for the duration of the new project. The position of a Young Researcher (a special position for young people to obtain a PhD financed by the Slovenian Research Agency) is the only one to follow formal requirement practices, which depend on both the individual merits of an academic and the position available. The status of a Young Researcher is a temporary position, lasting 3.5 years. Although a joint committee at the ZRC SAZU level is formed for the position of a Young Researcher, its members more or less just confirm the candidate selected by the Heads of the institutes and mentors, and ensure that the protocol is fully followed.

Therefore, the Heads of the institutions have a decisive role in the research policy creation and candidate selection processes. As they are responsible by the statute of ZRC SAZU for management of the institute and other operations, they also have a role in deciding about human resources and finances. Officially, the Scientific Committee of the institute should confirm each new employment as well, but institutes have differently considered this regulation and usually new candidates have been accepted without any selection process. In such a case, the HR officer informs the Employment Service of Slovenia about the job vacancy and the already known candidate without any detailed job description and requirements. In the institutions where the Scientific Committee collaborates in the recruitment process, nevertheless, its five members just evaluate the qualifications of the candidates proposed by the Head of the institution and make a decision. In some institutions, there is also an internal committee for the position of a Young Researcher, whose members are usually the Head of the institution, deputies to the Head or the leader of the institute’s research programme (bigger research projects financed by the Slovenian Research Agency) and selected mentors. However, in many cases the candidates for a Young Researcher are already known to the mentor or to the Head of the institute, usually a student of the mentor or his/her colleague. Unknown candidates rarely come to an

interview. In such cases, the Head of the institute has usually made inquiries about the candidate among colleagues.

The Director of ZRC SAZU forms the committee for the Young Researcher at the ZRC SAZU level each year. The members are specialised in different fields and come from different institutions.

5.2 SET UP OF THE TASK

Who participated in the reflexive working groups?

The invitation to the workshop was sent to all Heads of the institutions of ZRC SAZU and the leaders of the management unit at ZRC SAZU ten days before the meeting took place. Seven Heads of the institutes took part at the workshop, three members of the GARCIA team and the Director of ZRC SAZU. A foreign lecturer Dr. Muriel E Swijghuisen Reigersberg led the workshop. She is an ethnomusicologist, a Research Development and Policy Manager and a Visiting Fellow at the Music, Mind and Brain research centre, Psychology Department, Goldsmiths, University of London. Her managerial role includes collaborating on open access and data initiatives, ethics and integrity management, medical ethnomusicology and impact, performance studies, research ethics, and the relationship between music, health and wellbeing. From 2012 to 2015, she was a Visiting Research Fellow at the Department of Psychology, Goldsmiths. From 2012, she is working as a Head of Office at the Research Development department at the Goldsmiths Research Office (University of London). Since she is working in the field of the research development policy in Goldsmith and—as a researcher, represents an administrative person and a person who is involved in research—she is also competent for explaining the tools of how to become a more successful researcher.

The participants of the workshop were coming from several ZRC SAZU institutes: Institute of Philosophy, Fran Ramovš Institute of the Slovenian Language, Institute of Slovenian Ethnology, Karst Research Institute, Institute of Ethnomusicology and Institute of Culture and Memory Studies. Among the eight participants (Heads of the institutes and the Director), there were five men and three women. The Director of ZRC SAZU also participated in the workshop and was actively involved in the discussion.

Due to the small number of participants, we did not follow to the suggested plan of the workshop. While leading the workshop, the lecturer focused on the Slovenian specific situation in constructing scientific excellence, research development and the gained experiences. The lecturer also compared the situation in Slovenia with the situation in the UK and advised on how to resolve the current Slovenian situation by taking into account suggestions, based on the UK experience. The lecturer focused on two current problems – the problem of scientific excellence and the problem of research practices.

How did you set up the working groups? What questions did you ask? Did you use a specific form of group discussion to disseminate the results and encourage interpersonal learning and discussion?

The initial plan was to set up working groups in which all Head of the ZRC SAZU institutes and professors from the Biotechnical Faculty would be participating, but in the end, only Heads of the ZRC SAZU institutes participated. We invited Heads of the institutes because, according to the statute, they hold extensive powers and they also have the power to influence the recruitment processes. At ZRC SAZU, the main employment policy of the institutes is handled by the Heads of the institutes, whose roles, among others, include organisational management (e.g. planning, organising, developing and supervising research at the institute) and financial management. Each institute has a basic research programme that is led by the Head or an excellent researcher of the institute, and there are also basic research national and international projects and other applied activities. Based on the institute's programme and obtained projects, the Head, together with the leader of the programme and/or projects, decides on new employment needs. Furthermore, scientific committee of each institute must confirm the acceptance of a new candidate. Because of the Fiscal Balance Act, which has reduced new employment in the public sector, new employment (including those with a temporary contract) has to be confirmed by the Management Board of ZRC SAZU as well.

After the introduction, the lecturer presented the notion of 'scientific excellence' and the criteria for its measurement, and asked the participants about the challenges they are facing in their academic career. She pointed out that today it is expected from researchers to be a "Jack-of-all-Trades" while being good at everything they do. Nowadays, the situation is very different from twenty years ago, because researchers have to be able to do everything. They have to be a good writer, a great administrator and a good promoter of themselves. They have to be able to understand the legislation and politics, to be familiar with technologies and to be able to apply for grants. In addition, they have to be good at generating impact, engaging with the public, be open to the media, write good books and combine everything with their teaching responsibilities. Therefore, a huge pressure lies on academics and researchers of today, which needs to be acknowledged.

Afterwards, the lecturer presented the situation in the UK while focusing on funding and research development and on how to provide young people with the information to help them. The lecturer said that in the UK they have a dual support system in terms of the support from the government: 1. Manage the research excellence framework (the business of measuring) – you need to publish publications, which get peer reviewed, and according to your success, you are awarded with some money. 2. The higher education council, which is especially useful, because the government recognises that it is very difficult to get funding for some disciplines in arts and humanities.

The lecturer pointed out that research excellence is not really an objective fact. Colleagues who all have a role to play in assess it. In addition, peer review is not perfect, because there are many interpersonal issues you need to take into consideration. If your field of research is very small, there is a big chance you will probably know who your reviewer is. While talking about measuring excellence, the metrics (the number of citations) is also an imperfect system. Scientists in the arts and humanities field are in disadvantage because citation is the only measurement of their excellence. However, if you are an established scholar, you have the benefit from your reputation and some institutional support. For example, if you are at the beginning of your career, someone who still has to build a reputation, not many people will cite you. The lecturer pointed out that we need to ask

ourselves the following questions: How to support researchers? How to understand the challenges that researchers face?

What aspects were most discussed/most popular? Shortly discuss these.

Based on the presented situation, the lecturer focused on the problem of networking in Slovenia and abroad, cooperation with decision makers and the meaning of the administrative support of the institute, especially why it is important to have a good and reliable administrative support, which is a novelty for the Slovenian scientific sphere. Key topics in this context are focused on the people who work in the institution, the responsibilities each member holds and the importance of sharing the knowledge. An important remark was done by one of the participants who pointed out that it is very important from which country the researcher is coming from. Since Slovenia is a small country, this can sometimes represent an obstacle, because it does not have well-known or important institutions with a good administrative support that other, bigger countries have. Participants of the workshop pointed out that ministers in the government do not have enough authority due to their unsteady positions to convince the Minister of Finance to raise the level of quality in this field. In addition, in the last few years, the budget for science in Slovenia decreased by 25%. Consequently, there is no sufficient space for manoeuvring in the Slovenian scientific sphere, even for the decision makers within their research agency. The participants also pointed out that researchers are forced to work on 5 or 6 projects simultaneously due to the low finances involved, which is very chaotic.

While talking about networking, the lecturer pointed out the importance of national and especially international networking. She also advised the participants to engage into policy revisions and discussed the meaning of the administrative support. The lecturer presented some important links and pointed out their importance in the area of networking while talking about sharing knowledge. She recommended the link Concordat to Support the Career Development of Researchers (<https://www.vitae.ac.uk/policy/concordat-to-support-the-career-development-of-researchers>), which informs us about the agreement between funders and employers of research staff in order to improve the employment and support for researchers and research careers in the UK higher education. It sets out clear standards regarding what research staff can expect from the institution that employs them, as well as their responsibilities as researchers. The lecturer also pointed to the link Vitae about research development, mobility and reviews of the areas of strength (<https://www.vitae.ac.uk>), focusing on the potential of researchers.

Another aspect, which was the most discussed, was the importance of the administrative support of the institute. The lecturer, who cooperates in research development at the Goldsmith University, specialising in arts, humanities and social sciences, suggested that we need to find out what kind of administration we need in Slovenia and if researchers want to cooperate in an administrative support team. The lecturer's team is working with European projects, which involves a lot of paperwork – there is a lot of reporting involved, therefore many researchers would rather avoid it to be able to get on with the business of doing research. In the UK, they have acknowledged that this is an issue and as a result they have come to specialise their attention to the research development and support officers, managers etc. The lecturer dedicated particular attention to the problem of

researchers that they need to play many different roles – they have to be good researchers, provide administrative support, take care for their own promotion, and they are consequently and constantly confronted with new challenges.

There is a generational gap between senior and young academics, which are especially under pressure due to their non-permanent positions. The Director and other participants pointed out that most of the researchers do also provide administrative support. They have to be their own administrators, their own PR managers, write proposals and do their research, etc. The lecturer added that in the UK some universities invest a lot of money in administrative support. They send their staff to trainings in Brussels (to the European Commission) or join them into organisations to get the necessary skills. In the UK, they established ARMA – the professional research association for research managers and administrators, who are dealing with research contracts and research proposals. They created a policy role for the organisation; therefore, they directly respond to the government and encourage the academics to do the same.

Besides, researchers need to be well aware of the situation in science on a global and national level. An aspect, which was also discussed, was the notion of the impact and the fact that we need to think how we can improve research effects. In some disciplines, it is hard to measure the impact. The lecturer added that it depends if we are talking about a long-term or an immediate impact. In the UK, they included impact in their research assessments. Research can be quite impactful, but people do not know how to articulate the impact. One of the roles of the administrator would be to think about how to cooperate as an institute and improve the impact. Thinking creatively about an impact is also important. Slovenia (and its academic sphere) has to reach out and not just expect that people will come here. According to the lecturer, researchers would be more productive if their institutes would include full time contracts and allow them the opportunities to develop their skills, which include project managing, leadership etc. In addition, collaborative efforts are very important, as is networking for sharing knowledge/information for the greater good. The lecturer suggested making an action plan, which would provide self-reflexion for improving the state.

What aspects were least discussed/least popular? Shortly discuss these.

Due to the fact that we are currently facing basic problems in Slovenia, connected with how to achieve scientific excellence—the conditions for achieving scientific excellence are insufficient—we paid a bit less attention to the gender itself. We focused our interest on the understanding of gender through other perspectives (finances/grants, networking, and administrative support) in the Slovenian academic sphere. According to the interviews for the T.2 report, the biggest problems in Slovenia are the general conditions, which the agency defined for gaining projects and grants. Because Slovenia is currently facing this kind of issues, the problem of gender therefore is of secondary meaning.

What were the action points or recommendations that came out of the working groups?

Based on the examples from the United Kingdom, the lecturer presented ideas on how to improve scientific excellence. The lecturer pointed out to the self-initiative of the researchers, who need to be proactive and put many efforts to compete with someone who is maybe not so good but is coming from a good university. Based on examples from

the UK, the lecturer presented ideas on how to face all the challenges researchers are facing today. This served as useful information to apply to the situation of the Slovenian scientific sphere. She pointed out the usage of the internet, which offers new ways of engaging, advised to publish via open access (Electronic Depository, the Research Gate, Academia.edu profiles) to increase citation ratings, to engage in policy revisions, etc. If you are coming from a small country and institute, you have limited available tools and open access can be reasonably easy to achieve. In addition, researchers have to network among themselves, visit workshops, publish on the open access websites and journals, they need to specialise themselves in certain topics, to disseminate their work, promote themselves, etc. The lecturer pointed out that researchers have to educate themselves continuously.

Good mentorship is also important and the lecturer pointed out to the seniors' responsibility to look after the next generation. The systems in the institution are not established to support, promote and reward mentorship. It seems as an extra task that researchers have to do and it takes away the time for writing a book or researching. Consequently, students are not benefiting as much as they should. It is necessarily to recognise the systems inside the institutions for this support. To summarise, we could say that to be able to improve the state in science, it is important to join, understand and create a cultural environment, to trust the senior management, to have a good administration support, etc. The engagement plan ("here is what we are going to do") is also important, together with inviting other universities and asking them what they are doing, sharing the information, etc.

Does commitment exist among key players to use these action points/recommendations? Explain why/why not.

According to the feedback of the workshop, we can conclude that commitment to use these action points and recommendations does exist among key players. The Director of ZRC SAZU actively participated in the workshop. In the end, he promised that similar workshops would be held each year. He also showed an interest in knowing how to prepare workshops and how to connect researchers by asking the lecturer to get additional information. In addition, the Heads of the ZRC SAZU institutes showed an interest in further workshops with similar topics.

5.3 EVALUATION OF THE TASK

What worked for you when planning and performing the working groups?

While we were planning and performing the working groups, we realised that the huge privilege of our research group is the fact that the Director was part of our group, because in this way, he was actively helping us to perform workshops. Nevertheless, he was the one who called the Heads of the ZRC SAZU institutes to participate in the workshop. Due to a lack of this kind of support at the Biological Faculty, we were less successful in inviting Professors and persuading them to cooperate in the workshops. The Director showed a lot of interest in the workshop because he would like to improve the current situation at ZRC SAZU.

The content of the workshop was focused on problems that ZRC SAZU and the wider Slovenian scientific sphere is currently facing, therefore, besides problematising gender in academia, we dedicated a lot of attention to the general notion of scientific excellence. This does not mean that Slovenia is not facing the problem of gender inequality, but only that we are probably less aware of this problem and therefore we invited a lecturer from another area of expertise.

What challenges and resistances have you come across when planning and performing the working groups? How did you overcome them (or not)?

The main challenge and resistance that we came across when planning and performing the working groups was that the Biological Faculty did not respond to the invitation. We were not able to overcome this challenge. We suggest that it would be wisely to rethink whom to invite as a lecturer in the working team to be able to perform successful workshops and disseminations in the future. It is also worth to mention the fact that the participation of the Heads of the ZRC SAZU institutes and especially the Director's participation were very welcome, because the Director has the power and also the charisma to invite his colleagues.

What are the learning points you gained from planning and performing the working groups?

One of the learning points we would like to describe is that it is very important that directors are part of the group in a workshop. It is important to choose the right time and perhaps we chose a bad one, because during the summer, people go on vacation, therefore they cannot participate in workshops. We would also like to suggest that the lecturer should be informed in advance about the particular situation in (Slovenian) science so she/he could be even more concrete in applying her/his knowledge to the particular national situation and the work in a group would give better results. Another learning point which we gained is that Heads of the ZRC SAZU institutes in Slovenia are quite interested in this kind of workshops, especially those who would like to continue their research work and stay in academia. All participants agreed upon further organisation of similar workshops as a regular practice.

What feedback did you get from participants?

The feedback from participants was positive in general. All participants of the workshop were pleased or very pleased with the content of the workshop, its relevance and its performance. They all agreed upon the suggestion that this kind of workshops should be organised in the future as a regular practice. The Director suggested that ZRC SAZU should organise a workshop at least once or twice a year to invite similar lecturers, who are experts in their field. He asked the lecturer if he should invite the participants who are early researchers together with the senior members to the same workshop. The lecturer advised that doing a workshop together is a useful thing, but you need to explain the both sides of the story – to explain what is 'scientific excellence' to young academics who are not yet familiar with the topic and also to provide useful knowledge for senior people to encourage them to go on.

New insights were gained by the participants in terms of importance of ensuring an inside pre-evaluation of project suggestions, especially if ZRC is the leading partner. In addition, that cooperation between co-workers is necessary and the lecturer pointed out the

meaning of the professional administrative support in the process of project application. The lecturer's argument was that if we have a good administrative support, we could bring more money. She suggested inviting many academics and creating a database about the information for which grants they are applying for. In this way, it is possible to show that over a few years' time the number of applications they produce is increasing.

Some participants pointed out that the lecturer should be more familiar with the specific Slovenian problems and local specialties to be able to help in the process of forming more useful suggestions for improvements.

What was specific for your context, which future leaders of working group need to take into account?

Specific for our Slovenian context, which future leaders of working group need to take into account, is the situation in the scientific sphere. After Slovenia's independence (1991), the process of introducing capitalist logic and acceptance of neoliberal paradigms started gradually, which caused "managerialism" in Slovenian science and research, and construction of excellence based on the global academic system grounded in the Western norm of meritocracy. Inclusion of Slovenian research centres and universities in the system for obtaining EU funds and the introduction of the continuous measurement of the internationally comparable quality of researchers, research groups, research institutions and universities have brought about a shift in emphasis from the quality of research to the quantity of published articles in highly-rated journals, which only count when written in English.

The Director stated that Slovenia is a small country with a small system. According to the results of some studies, this is a disadvantage. The traditional Slovenian scientific habitus is also problematic. The infrastructure still needs to be constructed. He also stated the differences between the UK and the Slovenian system while saying that there is a unique system of financing in Slovenia, because 80% of the budget comes from national or international calls. The problem is also that there are no fixed schedules. Besides, there exists a modern pragmatism, according to which you have to be innovative, practical and apply your new knowledge right away, like the colleagues in natural sciences. In Slovenia, there is access to the decision makers, but usually after they get familiar with good cases and practices from abroad, they, in most cases, do not apply them in Slovenia.

Unfortunately, projects have become a fundamental form of research work in Slovenian science, especially at the research institutes, and the struggle for funding has become the main preoccupation of researchers in order to survive. The result of the economic and social crisis from 2011 and the related reforms from 2012 (Fiscal Balance Act) have caused research funds to be cut each year and prolongation of the dates of national calls for research proposals, which caused an uncertain financial situation in scientific institutions. Furthermore, financing mostly depends on quantitative merits and usually money for research goes to people who have the best conditions to publish articles, though they are not necessarily also the best researchers. Another huge problem is also that the projects are strongly lobbied and there is no objective evaluation and selection.

5.4 CONCLUSION

Compare the set-up and evaluation of the working groups in the two departments. What similarities and what differences did you encounter?

The workshop was performed only at ZRC SAZU due to the lack of interest from the Biotechnical Faculty. However, it is worth to point out that participants were coming also from the STEM departments (institute) that are situated at ZRC SAZU. The discussion did not show any differences among them because STEM participants were not active in the debate. Concerning the problems with the agency and the scientific excellence criteria, we are all facing similar problems.

To what extent do you see the reflexive working groups as a feasible instrument to create or increase gender awareness among appointment committee members?

We largely see the workshop as a feasible instrument to create and increase gender awareness among appointment committee members. Due to other issues present in the Slovenian scientific sphere, the gender issue was one of the important topics, but not the only one. In our opinion, if we expose gender too much, participants do not attend working groups/workshops and they do not participate in the debate. This (and other) reasons forced us to strategically perform the workshop in a way that gender was only one criteria among several others (finances/grants, networking, administrative support), because in Slovenia, questions connected to gender are only at the stage of “raising awareness”. In addition, the lecturer should be more familiar with the question of gender and to be able to clearly distinguish the topic of gender inequalities from other topics connected with the issue of scientific excellence. Further, we as organisers (GARCIA team) should be more proactive in leading the workshop, especially the discussion, and remind the lecturer during her lectures to focus on gender issues more often.

What were the main action points or recommendations in the two departments to counter gender inequality in recruitment and selection decisions?

To summarise, the main action points or recommendations in the departments of ZRC SAZU (as already stated, we did not get any feedback from the Biotechnical Faculty) to counter gender inequality in recruitment and selection decisions, we can point out that while the workshop was based on the gender issue, there are many other issues currently present in the Slovenian scientific sphere, which are of utmost importance (finances/grants, networking, administrative support) in connection with gender, which we also had to take into consideration. In the context of the gender issue, the lecturer pointed out to the problem of women in science just briefly, but otherwise the main debate was focused on basic problems, such as finances/grants, networking, and administrative support, which are currently presents issues in the Slovenian academic sphere and they are far from being solved. The discussion on these issues provided us with very important information about the understanding of gender, which always needs to be understood through the intersectional perspective – at the crossroads of other social/academic phenomena. While organising and performing the workshop, we tried to capitalise on the much appreciated knowledge and skills of the lecturer, whose expertise is interdisciplinary, while deriving from theory and practice, to be able to better understand other issues, connected with gender in academia, which are perhaps not obvious at first sight, but not less problematic.

While talking about gender issues, the lecturer pointed out that administrators in the UK perform a survey to find out how happy the researchers are and if there is any additional support that they would need. Moreover, they ask the researchers what the institution can do to help them. Because they try to put a person's life in the context of his/her work, they are important for people with less opportunities, such as women in particular, because they are usually the care givers in their home and make sacrifices more often than men. Women also struggle more, because they are cited less. The research from the UK showed that not only women are applying less for grants but also that they are statistically getting fewer grants in comparison to men. The lecturer pointed out to another aspect, which is that women will often wait to be invited into a project, but men say clearly: "Include me!" In addition, there are strong struggles between genders and women have to show more research results and knowledge than their male colleagues.

Usually, Heads of institutes, Professors and Directors are aware of gender equality, they know what positive gender discriminations means, and recognise the importance of gender quotas and other policies, but subconsciously they still produce gender inequality, as these attitudes are strongly rooted in the academic habitus and embedded into the structure of institutions. Therefore, there should be more public discussion regarding gender emancipation and values that each gender embodies, and how to use this to optimise successful teamwork. The suggested future workshops by the Director of ZRC SAZU and the idea to invite similar lecturers, who are experts in their fields, seems to be a step in the right direction.

6. SWITZERLAND

6.1 INTRODUCTION

Because we are lucky to work in an institution where there is a relatively high level of institutionalised Gender Studies teaching and research and a long history of gender equality measures, we decided to take the existing actions at the UNIL in relation to the selection criteria used by academic recruitment boards as the starting point for our GARCIA Action plan.

As already noted in the reports for tasks 7.1 and 7.2, we encountered some structural problems in undertaking task 7.3 according to the guidelines provided by the Dutch team. This was because appointment procedures to many of the – numerous - postdoc positions at the UNIL, were not as formalised as they are for professorships.

Perhaps the most important problem lies in the very definition of the category of “post-doc” in the Swiss context. As we have noted in previous GARCIA reports, this category doesn’t correspond to a single status or type of employment contract. The “post doc” category is also extremely heterogeneous within our institution. Since the Swiss academic employment structure is very “bottom heavy”, there are few professorships (or tenured equivalent positions) and a very large number of fixed-term teaching and research positions that are usually considered to offer a “stepping stone” towards an academic career, but which do not necessarily lead on to a professorship within 10 or 15 years after the PhD.

At the UNIL, a “post doc” can be hired at very different stages in their academic career (e.g. just after having obtained his/her PhD or many years later, having already occupied several other “post doc” positions, in Switzerland or abroad) and to positions that are not necessarily clearly identified as “post doc”. In 2015, the UNIL carried out a major census of its so-called “relief team” (the generic term used in French to designate a person who is potentially on an academic career track is *relève*). This survey served to illustrate the huge diversity amongst this category, which covers at least 4 sub-groups:

- **Post-doc assistants**, who are recruited by the Faculties or Institutes to perform teaching and research duties (usually in some kind of combination), and who are funded through the main cantonal budget (i.e. structural funds). The employment contracts are fixed-term, with a 1 + 2 + 2 format (a 12 months contract to begin with, potentially followed by two successive 24 month contracts). Renewal depends both on performance (the opinion of the professor in charge of the position is requested, but there is no formal appraisal procedure or formal evaluation process) and on the availability of funds. It is not possible to have more than one (5 year) post-doc assistantship within the same institution, but there is nothing to stop an individual to move to a second position in a different university. At the UNIL, these positions are usually funded from the budget allocated to funding PhDs. Within a given Faculty, no more than 20% of this budget can be allocated to post-doc assistants at any time. Thus, a professor who requests the creation of a post-doc assistantship will usually be required to renounce on a funded PhD position for a number of years, in compensation. However, it is not possible for a former PhD Assistant to be

recruited directly as post-doc assistant at the UNIL; he or she must first spend at least 1 year in another institution (preferably abroad), before returning to the UNIL.

- **Post-doc researchers** (usually called “SNSF Senior” post-doc positions), who are recruited (usually by individual professors or small research teams) to work on externally funded research projects. The duration of these positions is determined by the funding available, but is usually for 12 to 24 months. Generally speaking, these positions do not involve any teaching duties. Most of them are funded via competitive SNSF research project funding; other funding sources are more frequent in some faculties than in others. It is formally possible for someone who has just received a PhD from the UNIL to be recruited directly as a SNSF post-doc, but this is extremely rare. In most cases the “12 months obligatory mobility clause” (cf. for post-doc assistants) is usually applied to externally funded former PhDs too.
- In addition to these main “post-doc” positions, people with PhDs can also be recruited to temporary (PAST) or “tenure track” (PAST PTC) **Assistant professorships** and/or temporary (MA) or “tenure track” (MA > MER) **Senior Lectureships**. These are extremely rare in both the STEM and SHS Faculties and represent a negligible proportion of all post-docs at the UNIL and in Switzerland more generally. In some cases, these positions are funded (directly to the candidates themselves, as it were) through the SNSF programme to support young researchers. Much like the European Science Foundation schemes, the SNSF Ambizione and SNSF Professorship programmes enable “promising”, highly selected young researchers to receive a funding package, which includes their own salary and money to cover research costs (usually including salaries for at least 1 PhD student or post-doc) and to take this to the institution of their choice. In this case, the recruitment procedure takes place entirely outside the host institutions, by interdisciplinary, national selection boards, composed of representatives of different Swiss universities and disciplinary fields¹. Although numbers are very small, internal SNSF monitoring data suggests that there is no gender gap in the success rate of male and female applicants to these positions.
- Finally, an undetermined number of “post-docs” can be recruited to work on (usually externally funded) research projects on **Technical and Administrative Staff (PAT) contracts** that can either be permanent or fixed-term, full or part-time. Of all the post-docs in Switzerland, this is probably the most “hard to reach” category, notably because the content of their work is not necessarily seen as directly related to academic endeavours, although we know that this is often the case in practice. This is one of the strategies that can be adopted in order to continue employing post-doc assistants who have already completed their 5-year contract and who still don’t have any other employment opportunities outside the UNIL.

¹ See GARCIA Report 7.1, point 2, “Formal recruitment procedures and criteria at all levels of the university” for more detailed information on this point.

As shown in Figure 1, the number of post-docs has increased in both departments over the last five years (+ 21% for PhD students and + 29% for postdocs).

Figure 6.1. Number of PhD students and postdocs between 2010 and 2014.

Source: Workshop “Postdocs@UNIL: What’s new”, Lausanne, UNIL, 18.11.2015.

In 2015, there were approximately 350 full-time equivalent post-doc assistantships and FNS-funded post-docs working at the UNIL. University statistics do not enable us to calculate the precise share of each of these types of contract, nor the gender composition of this “post doc” workforce. The main post-doc categories (post-doc Assistants + SNSF Senior post-docs) make up 10.8% of staff in the SSP (SHS) Faculty, as compared to 22.4% in the STEM (FBM) Faculty. However, much of this difference is explained by the larger share of PhDs (and smaller share of tenured positions) in the Social than in the Medical Sciences.

Because of this diversity of employment and working conditions for UNIL “post-docs”, it is not always easy: (1) to identify who had been involved in the selection procedure of postdocs, since there is no legal obligation for the Faculties to record this information, or to make it publically available; (2) to identify the criteria mobilised in the selection process, since that were not clearly defined and are likely to vary according to the type of post-doc position under consideration.

The University Directive 1.34 provides guidelines for the recruitment of PhD assistants and post-doc assistants, it mainly stresses the formal recruitment procedures (e.g. the composition and professional status of the recruitment board members), but does not mention any specific selection criteria. These are explicitly left to the employing organisation to determine, according to their teaching and/or research needs. Moreover, there are no written reports on nominations to most of these post-doc positions. In theory, all post-doc assistant positions now have to be advertised through the UNIL web site, but this may sometimes be a mere formality. In some Faculties, these positions are

only opened when a former PhD student has completed a post-doc period (usually 12 – 18 months) abroad and – for various reasons – wants to return to his or her “home” institution, notably to continue collaboration with his/her former PhD supervisor or research team.

Table 6.1. The share of PhD and post-doc positions as compared to permanent academic positions, according to Faculty (full-time equivalent), 2015. Source: Direction UNIL (2016: 6).

Finally, we can note that there is little or no public debate about the recruitment procedures or criteria for this kind of position within the UNIL, whereas there is a lot of publically expressed concern and many policy recommendations concerning professorial nominations.

For all these reasons, a lot of our gender awareness activities were aimed at the members of professorial recruitment boards, since these are also the people who are most likely to be involved in hiring postdocs. We can only hope that our actions to raise awareness on the intersections of power and gender relations in professorial hiring committees are also useful for hiring procedures at lower and less standardised levels.

In the next section (2), we present the actions undertaken under the GARCIA Action Plan for WP7. We report on the outcomes of these actions in section 3, before presenting the most noteworthy conclusions.

6.2 SET UP OF THE TASK

Since the early 2000s, four successive Federal Gender Equality programmes (FGEP) named “Equal opportunity in Universities” have demonstrated a tangible political will at federal level to promote women’s access to all levels of academic institutions. Each of these programmes has formulated several distinct but interrelated objectives for all Swiss universities:

1. Encouragement for the recruitment of more women to tenured academic positions;
2. Mentoring programmes for junior researchers;
3. Support for the development and institutionalisation of gender studies and research on equal opportunities and gender discrimination;
4. Measures to promote work-life balance in academic careers, including direct support for the provision of university-based day nurseries and/or emergency childcare services.

The fourth stage of the FGEP (2013-2016) entitled “Equal opportunity of women and men at universities/gender studies” (Swiss University Conference – Programme P-4) enabled each university to define its own priorities and objectives, in the form of a specific Gender Action Plan (GAP). The framework of the programme has the general goal of achieving 25% women among full professors at Swiss universities and 40% at the assistant professor level, as well as an increased proportion of women in decision-making bodies at universities and related institutions.

At the UNIL, this institutionally tailored plan has been further decentralised, in order to take internal (e.g. disciplinary) variations into account. Thus, each of the seven Faculties has been invited by the Rectorate to adapt the University-level GAP (Vision 50/50) to their particular profile and needs. Below (see points 2.2. and 2.3.), we will focus on the elements implemented of these GAP in the FBM and the SSP faculties to create gender awareness in hiring procedures after presenting actions designed by the Equal Opportunity Office (*Bureau de l'égalité* – BEC) for the whole UNIL.

6.2.1 Actions coordinated at university level

Article 1 of the UNIL Directive 0.2 on the “Promotion of equal opportunity at the University of Lausanne” stipulates that: “the Rectors’ Office of the University leads an active policy, especially regarding equality between women and men. The Rectors’ Office implements measures aimed at sustaining equal opportunity policies in practice” (Direction UNIL, 2006). To do so, the UNIL has set an objective, in its Gender Equality Action Plan 2013–2016, of hiring “at least one women for every four men” when recruiting for professorial positions by the end of 2016 (Canton de Vaud, 2013): “The general objective of the Rectors’ Office is to tackle the ‘leaky pipeline’ and ensure that, by 2016, 40% of appointments to a professorial rank are made to women,” and in line with this decision: “The theme of ‘equality’ has also been strengthened in the Faculties’ self-evaluation process and is one of the quality criteria” (Directorate UNIL-BEC, 2012).

A GAP at the level of the UNIL was already set up when the GARCIA project started in February 2014 and various actions that were compatible with the GARCIA objectives were on-going. We therefore decided to work in close collaboration with people or bodies already concerned by the UNIL and faculty GAPs. As some of us are elected members in various bodies linked to equality at central or faculty level, we were able to communicate extensively about the work performed in GARCIA:

- In August 2015, Nicky Le Feuvre was elected as Vice-Dean of the SSP Faculty, in charge of equality and early academic careers (*relève*);

- Farinaz Fassa is a member of the Gender Equality commission, a representative body of the UNIL;
- Nicky Le Feuvre and Farinaz Fassa are both members of the Gender Equality Delegation (see below for a description of this body);
- At the beginning of the GARCIA project, Nicky Le Feuvre was head of the Equality sector of the NCCR LIVES² (a research programme based in Lausanne with a network of about 180 researchers in six different universities); Farinaz Fassa succeeded her in January 2015 and, at the same time, Sabine Kradolfer was hired part-time as Equality Officer.

Equality delegation

Since 2006, the Rector's Office has encouraged the work of a number of Gender Equality "delegates", who are entitled to sit in, observe and report back on the work of the professorial recruitment Boards at the UNIL. According to the founding document of this advisory body: "In order to guarantee equality of treatment in recruitment processes [the Equality Delegation] members: 1) inform Recruitment Board members about the rules regarding gender equality at the University and 2) ensure that the rule of minority preference is applied when there is a need to choose between a male and a female candidate who have identical research and teaching qualifications and who are judged to be equally suited to an academic appointment" (Directorate UNIL, 2006).

Thus, once a job announcement (for an associate or full professorship) has been published, the secretary of the Equality Delegation invites members to volunteer to monitor the procedure. If an Equality delegate agrees to take on the task, s/he will become an official member of the Recruitment Board (without voting rights), will receive all the documents relating to the procedure, will take part in all the interviews and internal discussions, and will report back to the Equality Delegation chair on the results of the deliberation. In some rare cases, the final ranking of candidates proposed by the Recruitment Board has been refused by the Rector's Office, on the basis of the Equality delegate's report. For a number of years, the BEC and the Rectorate have been looking to improve the functioning of this Equality Delegation, which is a rather unwieldy body. Each Faculty is invited to nominate at least one "Equality delegate", who is then supposed to follow recruitment procedures outside his or her own Faculty (to avoid any conflict of interests during the deliberations) and to report back to the Chair (the Vice-Rector in charge of diversity and early academic careers).

Over the years, a number of difficulties have arisen with this set of arrangements, many of which have led to minor adjustments over time. Through previous discussions with the BEC, in plenary sessions and through our own experiences as Equality delegates, we had already identified the following points:

- There is a huge variety in the number of procedures followed by each individual delegate. Some members take on several nomination procedures each year or each semester, whereas others never respond to any invitation to volunteer;
- Participation is purely voluntary and is very time-consuming. Each nomination board sits 3 or 4 times within a 3 month period (first, to study all the applications,

² <https://www.lives-nccr.ch/en> (retrieved 24/06/2016).

define selection criteria and define a short-list, secondly, to read the publications of the candidates short-listed and to choose 3 – 4 candidates for a public lesson and interview; thirdly, to take part in the interviews and final discussion; finally, to verify and approve the recruitment report, or even to write a “minority report” in case of disagreement with the final recruitment recommendation);

- Being a member of the Delegation offers no compensation to members, who have to combine their work as gender equality delegate with the normal requirements to sit on various recruitment boards in their own Faculty or Department. This is particularly problematic for women in Faculties where female professors are scarce. In some cases, it has been possible to authorise delegates to fulfil a dual role (voting member + equality delegate) for procedures taking place in their own Faculty, but this also raises problems of impartiality;
- Although the whole Delegation meets in a plenary session at least twice a year, attendance from the least active members is often low and it is considered rather undiplomatic to suggest that passive members should be replaced, especially when they come from Faculties where gender equality issues are not seen as very important;
- Many faculties “forget” to inform the Delegation Chair about the launch of new procedures early enough in advance and it is then complicated for the delegate to adjust to the timetable of meetings decided in his or her absence;
- There is a high rate of turnover amongst the members of the Delegation, which is not conducive to the accumulation of shared experiences or the development of common “good practices”;
- There is a huge variety in the level of “gender awareness” amongst the delegates nominated by their respective Faculties and the BEC doesn’t provide any systematic training to prospective members (notably because of lack of resources and the high turn-over rate mentioned previously);
- It is rather challenging to follow a nomination procedure in a very unfamiliar disciplinary field. The criteria of excellence that seem to be obvious to members of the Board are not immediately clear to outsiders. Although this may sometimes be an advantage (asking innocently why one academic journal is considered to be so much better than another can stimulate critical discussion between the standard recruitment board members), it also makes it difficult to influence the final decisions;
- In those Faculties where the number of female professors is particularly low, there may not be a single women candidate for most of the positions advertised, making the equality delegate *de facto* redundant;
- Sometimes, the best person for a given position may not be one of the female candidates and this puts the equality delegates in quite a difficult position;
- Examples of blatant “old-fashioned” sexism would seem to be extremely rare amongst recruitment board members and it can be very difficult to identify and to know how to react to more subtle or “modern” forms of discrimination, especially without any form of gender awareness training;
- It is extremely difficult to establish the influence of the Equality delegates, since each recruitment procedure presents very specific characteristics. Even when the outcome is positive (a female candidate selected as *primo loco*), it is easy to

imagine that this would have been the case anyway, even without the intervention of the Equality Delegation. This is one of the reasons that motivated the BEC and the Vice-Rectorat to undertake a systematic evaluation of the work of the Equality Delegation in 2016.

As part of the GARCIA project, we offered to make a contribution to the evaluation of the Equality Delegation, with a view to improving the measures provided to promote women's access to professorships, at a time when the new four-year GAP (2017-2020) was due to be drafted. We were also interested in gaining a deeper insight into the challenges faced by Equality Delegation members, and some idea of the benefits identified by women applicants of having an "equality delegate" present during the recruitment process.

We thus organised a workshop to which we invited all past and present members of the Equality Delegation (n=43) to join us for a discussion on their experiences of being part of the delegation. In the invitation letter sent out in early May 2016, we announced that the workshop would provide the opportunity: (1) for them to describe their personal experience of taking part in hiring procedures on behalf of the Equality Delegation; and 2) to exchange views on this feedback and to put forward ideas for the future monitoring of appointment procedures.

As we knew that the end of the Spring semester is usually a very busy time in the academic calendar, we also devised a questionnaire (see Appendix 1), which was sent out to all potential participants, giving them the opportunity to respond in writing either before or after the workshop. This was to ensure that we would receive as much feedback as possible, despite potentially low participation rates. We received only seven completed questionnaires, all from colleagues (4 women and 3 men) who were unable to attend the workshop.

We initially planned to hold two workshops, both during the lunch-time break (food and drinks were to be provided, as added incentive to attend). Unfortunately, we received no applications for the 1st workshop (planned on June 8th), but 5 people (4 women and 1 man) registered for the session on June 20th. One person (a man) didn't turn up on the day and did not send any apologies, and one of the female participants was unable to attend because of a late incoming flight.

In the end, there were 6 participants in the workshop, including the head of the BEC, who also presented the preliminary results from the quantitative monitoring exercise that is currently underway.

Gender awareness video for hiring committees

The BEC was asked by the FBM (our STEM department) for a tool to create more awareness about gender stereotypes and on how discrimination mechanisms may operate during hiring procedures regarding the selection criteria and the adequacy of candidates to these criteria, in particular for women. It was decided to produce a short video clip (3 minutes) in collaboration with the Communication service of the UNIL and to present the video to all hiring committees in the whole of UNIL (and not only in FBM).

The GARCIA team was invited to join this project that will end with the release of the video at the beginning of the Autumn semester 2016 - 2017. We therefore took part (as experts and observers) in the discussions with members of the Equality commission (5 women and 3 men) during two meetings (16th and 26th of October 2016) regarding the content and format of the video and we had access to all information related to this project that was supplied by the BEC. We also contributed to this action by co-financing the production of the video.

6.2.2 STEM department

The adoption of the “decentralised” fourth stage of the FGEP (2013-2016) for equal opportunity policies coincided with the election of the first female Dean at the FBM. Under her leadership, the Faculty set up an internal working group, with the brief of elaborating an ambitious GAP for the Faculty, entitled “ACTION for equality”.³ This document was approved by the Faculty Council and has led to the recruitment of a Faculty “gender equality officer”, who is in charge of implementing the different dimensions of the GAP, whose main focus is to identify women with high potential who could reach professorial positions in the future. Recognising that it may face particular difficulties, a specific target of 25% of women in all new appointments to professorial positions has been set for the FBM Faculty instead of the Rectors’ Office general objective of 40% in 2016.

In early November 2014, we organised a meeting with the officer in charge of early career stage academics (*Commission de la relève*) and the Equality officer of the Faculty. As a result of this contact, since December 2014, we have been invited to join the Faculty Equal Opportunity Commission (*Commission Pro Femmes*) – hereafter EOC-FBM – as participant observers. We were really interested in participating in one or more meetings of the *Commission de la relève*, first to organise the focus group for task 7.1.2 (we asked to have some time, 30 minutes to 1 hour, at the end of one meeting), and later also to discuss with the professors who are member of this permanent commission, whose role is to hire or promote candidates to middle range MA, MER and Privat Docent positions, in a faculty which seems to be more resistant to gender equality than our SSH department. Despite our repeated requests we never managed to be invited to this Commission which meets 8 to 10 times a year – time / diary overload being the most repeated reason for denying us participation.

The Vice-Dean in charge of early career stage academics was running a project to introduce an additional criterion in the selection and promotion procedures for physicians, namely their clinical experience.⁴ Even if our target department is the section for basic sciences and not the section for clinical sciences of the FBM, it is interesting to note the willingness of the Faculty to add new criteria (or revalorise one) to the more “classical” ones (research and teaching) that define “excellence”. In the same line, the

³ <http://www.unil.ch/fbm/home/menuinst/la-faculte/egalite-femmes-hommes/plan-daction-de-la-fbm.html> (retrieved 24/06/2015).

⁴ For more information regarding the new criteria, see: http://www.unil.ch/fbm/files/live/sites/fbm/files/shared/akarlen/CCP/ Directive_%20CDir_politique_promotion_Vz_%255BADOPTEE_CDIRE_09.10.14_%255D.pdf (retrieved 08/07/2015).

“traditional” bibliometric indicators inspired by the “hard sciences” are less rigid regarding the performance of research and more open to other criteria like clinical experience. Therefore, according to the officer responsible for implementing these changes, candidates can better valorise their different competencies, and people (women?) who have a more multitask and multifunction profile (with clinical experience, research and teaching) can now compete with other those candidates (men?) who are highly specialised in only one particular domain (research). This new system will be evaluated for the first time after two years of implementation.

Before we started to collaborate with the EOC-FBM they had drawn up a checklist to be handed out to the members of the hiring committees to ensure that all steps of the procedure had been correctly completed. On this checklist, each member has to give his/her evaluation of the competencies of each candidate. During the meetings of the EOC-FBM, we soon went beyond our position as participant observers to act sometimes as experts, whose voices are listened to and who are thanked for their advice. We were also invited to take part in a sub-group of the commission in charge of pro-active early identification of women with high academic potential.

6.2.3 SSH department

The SSP Faculty has one of the highest rates of female professors in the whole of Switzerland (36% in 2015, as against a national average of 21%) and women are also well represented amongst the PhD students (60% of the funded-PhD assistants, for example). Contrary to the situation in the STEM department, the Faculty gives the illusion of having achieved gender equality (over 53% of all staff are women), despite a very unequal distribution of women at the different hierarchical levels. Thus, at the top the academic career structure, there is still a clear problem with vertical segregation, since women make up 40% of all associate and tenure-track professorships, but only 28% of full professors.

Given the “egalitarian appearance” of the Faculty, it has been rather more complicated to mobilise the decision-making bodies of the SSP Faculty around the definition of a tailor-made GAP. An internal working group was set up in 2013, under the responsibility of the Vice-Dean in charge of early academic careers. A provisional GAP was produced and adopted by the Faculty Council the following year, but a number of the concrete measures envisaged in this document were judged “unworkable” by the Rector’s Office, notably because they contravened university regulations on hiring practices, promotions or career management. Unfortunately, the (male) Vice-Dean in charge of revising this first version of the GAP fell ill and was not replaced, leaving the Faculty without a strategic GAP to put into practice.

The SSP Faculty was nevertheless quite active on the gender equality scene at the UNIL more generally, notably through close collaboration with the BEC on a number of “gender awareness training sessions” organized through the equality programme of the NCCR LIVES.

In 2014, under some pressure from the Rector and the BEC, the Faculty set up a new working group, under the chair of an Associate professor in Gender studies, which was

requested to revise the previous GAP. In order to achieve this objective, the new working group (made up of representatives of all of the Faculties staff categories) decided to field a questionnaire, similar to the one that had been used previously in the FBM and other Faculties, as a basis for their own GAPs. This process took quite a lot of time and energy, but revealed some interesting results, notably concerning the quite high levels of perceived discrimination amongst the intermediate levels of female academic staff. However, once again, the report produced by this working group, that was presented to the Faculty council in June 2015, does not include a precise GAP, only some recommendations about possible areas of intervention. The duty of finalising this document has since been delegated to the new Vice-Dean in charge of early academic careers and equality, who will be assisted in this task by a temporary “Equality Committee”, which has still to be elected.

Therefore, although the SSP Faculty does still not have an official GAP that could be considered equivalent to the “ACTION for Equality” initiative of the STEM department, one could argue that equality issues are actually more visible and more central to the preoccupations of the Faculty than in other disciplinary environments of the UNIL.

For the SHS department, we decided to organise a workshop (see Appendix 2) entitled “Gender and management: The case of academic organisations,” in October 2015, in the frame of the “Gender awareness training of the NCCR LIVES” and in collaboration with the BEC. This workshop, given by a Swedish colleague, Prof. Anna Wahl, was specially designed for academic staff and senior researchers (Professors and MER) who are in charge of research teams and are therefore members of hiring committees and who hire postdoc researchers. The invitation to the workshop was addressed to the senior members of the NCCR LIVES (+/-70 persons), and to the professors of various faculties (SSP, Arts, Geosciences and environment, Economics, Theology and Religious sciences). Only 8 persons (all women) registered for the workshop, and most of them were linked either to the GARCIA project, or to the Equal opportunity office. Only one “external” woman registered.

6.3 EVALUATION OF THE TASK

6.3.1 Actions coordinated at university level

Equality delegation

During the workshop with past and present members of the Equality delegation and in the questionnaires we received back from persons who could not attend, some topics arose clearly.

The lack of enough women full and/or associate professors who can serve in the different committees and commissions or in the executive bodies of the University or the Faculties was pointed out (in particular in the STEM and law faculties). As women in such positions are somewhat rare, they might be asked to take part in many more administrative activities than their male colleagues, which could have negative consequences for their own career advancement.

Not only appointment committees were at stake, but also Academic Planification Committees who have to identify the strategic development of the faculties in terms of

research and teaching and, as a consequence, the profile of the position that will be opened in the future or for the replacement of professors about to retire. Each faculty defines the rules for serving on such a Committee and, for example, in SSP, there are 11 members: the Dean, who chairs the sessions, six professors and among them the directors of the four institutes which constitute the Faculty, two external experts, one member of the PhDs and post-docs (*corps intermédiaire* – see report 7.1 for a detailed definition of this kind of position), one student member. Having the Dean and the four institute directors in this body, and knowing that women are less represented in such positions, it becomes clear that the commission is highly masculine, even in a faculty with a high number of women professors.

When a position is opened, the detailed indication of the position's profile (with clear requirements in terms of competencies, research, teaching and administrative experience) seems for some of our interviewees to work more transparently regarding the hiring criteria. One person explained she took part in a hiring committee where the profile of the position was really open and it enabled the committee to "choose according to the candidates" (ED-1)⁵ to hire people on the basis of their networks and academic affinities. Another person related a similar experience, but in this case, the chair of the committee decided to open the profile more widely to enable some women to be shortlisted.

In the shortlisting of the candidates, the presence of a member of the delegation can avoid sexism and the activation of stereotypes. One person (ED-4) remembered a case "where the report was completely stereotyped. It presented a 'promising' young (male) candidate and a young woman who had 'inflated ideas' of the topics she thought she could cover. He was presented as a young candidate who would be able to do everything, although he actually had fewer publications than the female candidate." The person had to intervene to raise awareness among the committee members that the woman had better scientific outputs than the man and that she was in fact able to achieve the research plan she had presented while it was not so obvious for the man.

This point raises the question of the scientific role the delegate should perform in the committee. If the person is too close to the vacant position, his/her impartiality can be questioned, while if s/he is too far from the field, his/her opinion can be considered to be scientifically irrelevant. Some persons recognise that they are not sufficiently aware of the way gender stereotypes and gender inequalities are constructed in the committees' deliberations and they are not sure they always act as well as they would like to.

Nevertheless, all think that the presence of a delegate is a positive point when this person (1) insists that all Board members are informed about / aware of the UNIL gender preference rule in favour of women (2) reminds board members about the low representation of women professors in the field in question and (3) monitors the decisions of the board members at regular stages throughout the procedure. This enables delegates to have more women shortlisted and sometimes appointed and "there's a kind of safety mechanism, at least it prevents them from stitching it up entirely in-house" (ED-1). This is

⁵ ED refers to the Equality Delegation and the number to the person who is speaking. As only women attended our meeting and as they are all professors, we decided not to give any further information, for confidentiality reasons.

particularly the case when the recruitment board chair of the committee is already gender-sensitive. But some of the points the delegate should raise could also be made by others, for example by members of the HR department who could help evaluate the candidates with more standardised criteria on the basis of a first analysis of the CV. The trend towards a more administrative analysis of the CV was debated and while some workshop participants recognised the importance of standardisation, they also observed that the quality of the journals in which the candidates have published will always be a vital indicator of “quality” for recruitment board members.

The delegates think that more statistics are needed and that those that are available (for example thanks to the monitoring done by the BEC) should be better publicised – for example, on the homepage of the faculty websites, or handed out to all the members of a hiring committee. They also think it would be interesting to ask the committee to explain the choices they made in relation to the sex of the candidates in one mandatory chapter of the report that should also take in account the gendered statistics in the field, department or faculty.

Gender awareness video for hiring committees

In the video clip, the importance of the quality of the work performed by the commission will be underlined, and gender is part of the quality, in particular in a university where the number of women professors should increase. Therefore, particular attention should be paid to the (conscious and unconscious) gender stereotypes that may be activated during the procedure. Everybody is influenced by stereotypes and the important point here is to be able to identify them, in particular when minority groups (women) are in contact with majority groups (men). Examples of negative stereotypes against women taken from scientific research will then be presented to raise awareness among the members of the hiring committees. We hope to be able to launch the video at the GARCIA Swiss National Conference in November 2016.

6.3.2 STEM department

The systematic denial of any gender discrimination in selection criteria and recruitment practices seems to be linked to the explanation of lesser research activities performed by people (women) asking to work on a part-time basis in the dominant extended-work-time culture of our STEM department. Despite their strongly rejecting any hint of gender discrimination, there is a clear sense that FBM professors believe that the only possible condition for women’s progression through the academic hierarchy is for them to adopt the employment practices that have historically been the prerogative of (married) men. Therefore, work-life balance arrangements such as a grant for women taking maternity leave enabling them to contract an assistant to replace them and to advance in their research during their leave was created in 2014.⁶

During our participation in the EOC-FBM, a special subsidy was created to encourage women’s inclusion as speakers in scientific events: “With a view to encouraging a greater number of female main speakers in the scientific events of the FBM and the CHUV, the

⁶ <http://www.unil.ch/fbm/home/menuintst/faculte/egalite-femmes-hommes/poste-de-soutien.html> (retrieved 24/06/2016).

Dean's Office has issued a directive coming into force on 1 January 2016. It gives the FBM departments and CHUV services access to a subsidy for the organisation of scientific event with a minimum of 40% women speakers."⁷

A meeting with the Dean is arranged in August 2016 to discuss the possibility of increasing the number of women shortlisted in hiring procedures. Two formal proposals under discussion: the creation of a double shortlist, one for male candidates and another for women; or the concentration of the names of all shortlisted women at the beginning of the list to highlight them.

As our agenda and that of the EOC-FBM did not have the same priorities and time-lines, we were unable to organise a workshop for committee members specific to the FBM, but the EOC-FBM is planning an action in September 2016 specially directed to women professors to create a women's network, along with a conference directed to the whole faculty. It is really important to them that this event should not appear as "too feminist or too militant", in order not to discourage part of the potential public. We will see how we could further participate to such kinds of actions until the end of the GARCIA project.

One of the problems of this faculty is to have women on boards, commissions, committees, etc. because of the small number of women associate and full professors.

6.3.3 SSH department

This faculty has experimented with an increase in women's share of academic positions over the past years, but members of the faculty usually think that "more could be done" (either by women themselves, or by the institution). There is also a relatively strong "equality culture" in this faculty. We therefore decided to offer a rather specialised workshop with Prof. Anna Wahl. She pointed out that universities are gendered organisations with homosocial cultures where the masculine is the norm and that this has effects on the selection and evaluation of women. Regarding the selection of young researchers, she showed that women tend to be evaluated on what they have already accomplished while men are evaluated in relation to what they will achieve in the future, their supposed potential. She invited the participants to think about possible ways to change the gendered structures and culture in academia and to deal with resistance to changes. Participants then had to work in small groups on various practical exercises.

6.4 CONCLUSION

For all the actions we participated in or organised, we had problems in getting people involved, especially when they are not really concerned about gender inequalities, or which they may nevertheless be "aware". If we are not able to motivate them by offering them workshops they could identify with, we might need our authorities (deanship or rectorate) to ask them to take part in mandatory courses... but we also know that obliging someone to participate in a workshop she/he is not interested in is not really successful. An

⁷ <http://www.unil.ch/fbm/home/menuinst/faculte/egalite-femmes-hommes/subside-manifestations-oratrices.html> (retrieved 24/06/2016).

alternative to this would be to invite a well-known keynote speaker, announcing a conference on a more general scientific topic, which could end in a gender awareness talk.

One solution regarding the administrative work overload of women (in particular in highly masculine fields), which discourages some from taking part in a lot of committees, could be to reward them for their work with relief from other tasks (teaching activities) or giving them more sabbatical leaves. The University of Geneva is working in this direction by “professionalising” delegates, who are a limited number of persons all relieved of part of their teaching activities during their mandate.⁸

6.5 REFERENCES

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6.6 APPENDICES

Appendix 1.

Questionnaire on your experience of taking part in recruitment procedures as an equality delegate

The topics below are only suggested starting-points for your thoughts on your experience. Feel free to expand on some points and deal with others more briefly.

Gender (M/F).....

Faculty.....

In your activities as an equality delegate (including those where you had a dual role)
--

⁸ <https://www.unige.ch/rectorat/egalite/ancrage/delegation/> (retrieved 24/06/2016).

roughly how many *appointments committees* did you monitor?

What was the breakdown (in %) by Faculty?

.....FBMFGSEFTSRHECFDSCALettresSSP

What were your initial reasons for agreeing to be an equality delegate (committee member)?

What were your initial reservations when you offered to serve?

In the course of the procedures, did you feel that your presence helped to favour the recruitment of more women? If your experience was varied, please give some contrasting examples:

My presence had a positive influence when:

My presence did not have a positive influence when:

In these procedures, what were the situations in which you *felt useful*?

In these procedures, did you encounter situations that you judged clearly discriminatory towards a woman's candidature?

If so, how did they arise? At what stage in the procedure? For what type of post?

In those cases, were you able to react, and, if so, how?

If you had the opportunity to do it again, how would you react?

More generally, in those procedures, with what arguments did you most often intervene?

And what arguments did you deliberately avoid using?

Why?

In the light of your experience, what would be the most effective measures to promote women's academic careers in the Uni?

Anything you would like to add about those procedures?

Please return this form by June 20th 2016 to:

Appendix 2.

 EQUALITY OFFICE

GENDER AWARENESS TRAINING OF THE NCCR LIVES

**WORKSHOP “GENDER AND MANAGEMENT –
THE CASE OF ACADEMIC ORGANISATIONS”**

Organised by the Equality Office of the NCCR LIVES, the Equal Opportunity Office of the University of Lausanne and the GARCIA EU research project

Invited speaker: Professor Anna Wahl

University of Lausanne, Géopolis Building, Room 2137, 1015 Lausanne

Venue: <http://www.unil.ch/acces/en/home/menuguid/planete-unil.html>

October 22nd, 2015

9.00-12.30

**This workshop is specially designed for academic staff and senior researchers
(Professors and MER) who are in charge of research teams**

Participation is free of charge, but registration is mandatory (<https://www.lives-nccr.ch/en/gender-and-management>) before October 15th 2015.

We operate on a first come, first served basis, with priority given to members of the NCCR LIVES.

Organisers

- Equality Office, NCCR LIVES (Farinaz Fassa & Sabine Kradolfer)
- Equality Office of the University of Lausanne (Stefanie Brander & Carine Carvalho)
- GARCIA EU research project: <http://garciaproject.eu/>

For any further information, please contact the LIVES Equality Officer: Sabine Kradolfer, equality@lives-nccr.ch

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 EQUALITY OFFICE

Presentation

The workshop is divided into two parts. During the first part (9.00-10.30), the general theme of gender and organisations will be introduced, with a special focus on issues of structure, culture and management practices. The case of academic organisations will be highlighted as gendered perceptions of scientific excellence, potential and quality are particularly important here. During the second part of the workshop (11.00-12.30), the participants will work in smaller groups to discuss different forms of gender inequality in the academy and to explore ideas about working for change. There will be room for reflections on resistance to change and strategies for reducing gender inequalities on individual, group and institutional levels.

Speaker: Anna Wahl

Professor (Chair) Gender, Organisation and Management at the Royal Institute of Technology (KTH), Stockholm. Anna Wahl is a member of the Gender Equality Commission at Swiss National Science Foundation. Her current research interests include the gendering of management in different contexts, working for change and the impact of gender equality in organisations.

Her recent publications include contributions to: Leadership through the Gender Lens, (2010) Husu, Hearn, Lämsä and Vanhala (eds.), On the Shoulders of Giants (2011), Jenssen and Wilson (eds.), Gendering management (date?) In Sandberg, Åke (ed.) Nordic lights. Work, management and welfare in Scandinavia. Stockholm: SNS Förlag (2013) and NORA - Nordic Journal of Feminist and Gender Research (2014) Male managers challenging and reinforcing the male norm in management.

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